

AI-PRISM

D2.22 – Reference Framework and Specifications(II)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement n° 101058589. This document reflects only the author's view and the EU Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Project Title	AI-Powered human-centred Robot Interactions for Smart Manufacturing
Project Acronym	AI-PRISM
Grant Agreement No	101058589
Instrument	Research & Innovation Action
Topic	HORIZON-CL4-2021-TWIN-TRANSITION-01-01
Start Date of Project	October 1, 2022
Duration of Project	36 months

Name of the deliverable	Reference Framework and Specifications
Number of the deliverable	D2.2
Related WP number and name	WP2 AI-PRISM Architecture
Related task number and name	Task 2.1 AI-PRISM Reference Architecture Task 2.2 Usage Models and Mock-ups Task 2.3 Functional Specification Task 2.4 Technical Specification
Deliverable dissemination level	Public
Deliverable due date	30/09/2023
Deliverable submission date	29/09/2023
Task leader/Main author	TAU
Contributing partners	UPV, TAU, IKE, PIAP, TEK, ITI, FBK, NTT IT
Reviewer(s)	FBK, PIAP

Keywords

Reference Architecture, System Design, Technical Key Exploitable Results, Implementation Guidelines

Revisions

Version	Submission date	Comments	Author
v0.1	2023/01/13	ToC Submitted	Francisco Fraile
v0.2	2023/09/08	Document ready for internal revision	TAU
v1	2023/09/27	Document ready for second internal revision	TAU
v2	2023/09/29	Document ready for submission	TAU

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Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
AD	Ambient Digitalization
AGV	Automated Guided Vehicles
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AMR	Autonomous Mobile Robot
CD	Continuous Deployment
CDE	Continuous Delivery
CI	Continuous Integration
CM	Communication Modules
DDS	Data Distribution Service
DOA	Description of the Action
DR	Agent Level Reasoning Modules
DS	Data Platforms
eTaSL	A task specification language
HI	Human Machine Interaction Modules
HMI	Human Machine Interaction
HW	Hardware
IIoT	Industrial Internet of Things
IoT	Internet of Things
IT	Information Technology
MAC	Medium Access Control
NFV	Network Function Virtualization

OT	Operational Technology
PD	Programming with Demonstration
PE	Perception Enhancing
QDSN	Quick Deployment Sensor Network
QoS	Quality of Service
RA	Reference Architecture
RGB	Red Green Blue
ROS	Robot Operating System
SDN	Software Defined Networks
SE	Simulation Environment
SP	Human Safety Management Procedures
SSH	Social Sciences Humanities
TSN	Time Sensitive Networks
WSN	Wireless Sensor Networks

Executive summary

This deliverable describes the AI-PRISM reference architecture, which is an abstract, high-level description of the reference architecture of AI-PRISM. It also contains a high-level description of the different components of AI-PRISM, drafted in M3, and completed by M12. The objective is to build a common understanding of ‘what is AI-PRISM?’ that extends the definitions included in the DOA and that provides a common framework to further develop the answers to the questions: ‘how is AI-PRISM used?’ (answered in T2.2 – Usage Models and Mock-ups), ‘how does AI-PRISM work?’ (answered in T2.3 – Functional Specification), and ‘how is AI-PRISM implemented?’ (answered in T2.4 – Technical Specification).

The AI-PRISM project

AI-PRISM will provide industrial users with human-centred artificial intelligence (AI)-based solutions to create a more efficient, resilient, digital, sustainable, and high-quality European manufacturing industry.

To do so, we will develop an integrated and scalable environment with solutions adapted to dynamic and unpredictable manufacturing scenarios that require tasks that are difficult to automate and where speed and versatility are essential to meet users' needs. Furthermore, the solutions will be specific to semi-automated and collaborative manufacturing in flexible production processes and will not require specific robotic programming skills.

Our solutions ecosystem will have four main pillars:

1. A human-centred collaborative robotic platform oriented to ease hard-to-automate manufacturing tasks.
2. A human-robot cooperative environment powered by trustworthy AI.
3. Social human-agent-robots teams' collaboration — AI-based safety monitoring and robot control mechanisms to detect and avoid unsafe situations and ensure social and physical safety.
4. An open-access network portal to offer compliant infrastructure.

To evaluate our solutions' performance, transferability, scalability, and large-scale deployment, we will perform demonstrations in real operating environments. Specifically, in four user pilots involving key manufacturing sectors — furniture, food/beverage, built-in appliances, and electronics —, types of robots and industrial processes that are difficult to automate, plus a generic demonstration facility.

In addition to seeking quantitative improvements in the manufacturing sector, AI-PRISM aims to use technological innovation to support a paradigm shift in which AI, robotics and Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) are integrated into the manufacturing domain for the improvement of flexible production processes, becoming a viable and widespread alternative for European factories.

During the next three years, 25 partners from 12 countries will join forces to make AI-PRISM a reality. From educational institutions to research and technology organisations, robot manufacturers, industries and use case providers; our interdisciplinary consortium brings together all the actors of the human-robot collaboration value chain and involves key experts in SSH, standardisation, exploitation, and dissemination.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Objectives and Methodology

The first objective of this task is to deliver a reference architecture that frames the key technical results of AI-PRISM. The AI-PRISM Reference Architecture (RA) defines the technical structure and establishes the relations between the key technical results identified in the DOA. This way, the AI-PRISM RA will provide a template solution for the technical implementation in AI-PRISM, through the integration of the envisioned key technical results. In this sense, the DOA includes different types of technical results:

1. **Hardware components.** Hardware equipment required to deploy an AI-PRISM collaboration ambient.
2. **Communication networks.** Communication network equipment enabling real time communications in the collaboration ambient.
3. **Runtime Environments.** Components providing the execution environment for software components.
4. **Software components.** Components implementing the functions and behaviours of AI-PRISM.

First, the AI-PRISM RA establishes the relationships between hardware components, communication networks, runtime environments, and software components. Then, based on these relationships, this document describes the main characteristics, the candidate solutions that can be integrated and re-used, and the baseline specifications, defined as the minimum configuration necessary to instantiate an AI-PRISM collaboration ambient. Then, for each of the software components, this document provides a description, a list of functional components mapped to the AI-PRISM RA, and an indication of the expected input and output interfaces. Also, the main interactions between components will be identified, as well as interactions with functions outside the scope of AI-PRISM.

Delivering a low-level, detailed description of the interactions, procedures, or specifications of AI-PRISM technical results is out of the scope of this deliverable. Instead, the objective is to provide an abstract description of the technical architecture of AI-PRISM to identify the main equipment and communication networks involved, and how the different AI-PRISM components interact between them within this technical infrastructure. The adoption of this reference architecture will ensure the applicability and consistency of the key technical results of AI-PRISM. Another objective of this deliverable is to improve the interoperability of the different components, by establishing common mechanisms for the implementation of communication interfaces and by aligning the reference architecture with standards and industry best practices. Furthermore, the adoption of the reference

architecture will help to identify synergies and development assets common to several components. Later, during the implementation phase, AI-PRISM can provide a unified response to these common needs optimizing development efforts. Additionally, the AI-PRISM RA will provide a unified architectural view and will establish definitions for key concepts to promote a common understanding of the technical implementation of the pilot use cases.

To do this, the document first provides a brief description of the key technical results listed in the DOA, and will clarify the key concepts included in these definitions. This information is included in the next subsections. Then, section 2 will provide a reference architecture framing the different components and identify the different networks and equipment involved. Section 3 of the AI-PRISM RA will provide baseline specifications for networks and hardware equipment. Section 4 will provide a description of the main functions and interfaces of the different software components. Finally, section 5 will provide guidelines for the development of components and interfaces.

This document is part of the series of deliverables Reference Framework and Specifications, which conveys D2.1 Reference Framework and Specifications (I) delivered in M3, and D2.2 Reference Framework and Specifications (II), delivered in M12. D2.1 focuses on the overview of the key technical results described in the DOA, the establishment of the common terminology, and the definition of the AI-PRISM RA, so that this initial abstract description is defined as early as possible in the project. Then, based on these common system definitions, technical partners will iteratively complete the definitions of the internal functions and interfaces of components, making sure that they are consistent. A first complete, internal version of the Reference Framework and Specifications was delivered in M6, and the final version is completed and reported in D2.2 in M12. This timeline is depicted in Figure 1.

	2022			2023									
	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12	
Reference Architecture			v1										
Networks and Equipment			v1			v2						v3	
Runtime Environments			v1			v2						v3	
Software Components						v1						v2	
Implementation Guidelines			v1			v2						v3	
				D2.1								D2.2	

Figure 1: Reference Framework and Specifications timeline

In this sense, **choices** and specific technologies included in previous versions **at M3 and M6 are preliminary suggestions**, that can always be replaced by better alternatives, if and when the need arises. It is also important to highlight that the AI-PRISM specifications will continue to evolve during the execution of the project, in order to adapt to the dynamic environment of the pilot scenarios. An online version of the specifications is available in this link and will be periodically updated after M12.

The online specification contains further details of the specification that are summarised or omitted in this deliverable for brevity.

1.2. AI-PRISM Key Technical Results Overview

The following table provides an overview of the key technical results framed in the reference architecture.

Table 1: Technical Results

Technical Result	Description
AI-PRISM Human Centred Collaborative Robotic Platform	
AI-PRISM ROS Framework	Robot Operating System (ROS) Framework to manage the deployment of ROS modules. Core ROS (2) packages which together with a development guideline library will provide a technological common ground for the integration of the (AI-PRISM) functional modules.
AI-PRISM Base Hardware	Supported base hardware interfaces (for Automated Guided Vehicles (AGVs), mobile robots, industrial robots, etc). Dedicated drivers for supported Hardware (HW) modules for human/robot collaboration.
AI-PRISM Communications Modules	ROS packages that will enable real-time communication within the AI-PRISM Data Platform and with other devices.
AI-PRISM Ambient sensing infrastructure	Supported sensors and cameras to sense the environment. RGB and depth sensors will be employed to digitalize the working environment and the components acting in it, such as robotic agents, human workers, obstacles, and tools. The data acquired in the form of 2D visual content and 3D geometrical content will be fused to create textured 3D point clouds capturing the environment at a precise time frame. The scene reconstruction will be dynamically updated to account for dynamic agents moving in the environment. Additional sensors, such as thermal or infrared cameras, will be employed to consider complementary information. Algorithms to automatically calibrate such sensors will be provided.
AI-PRISM Real Time Communications Network	Supported real-time communication hardware. Software Defined Networks (SDN), Quick Deployment Sensor Network (QDSN), and Wireless Sensor Networks (WSN) sensor network control and management. The distributed nature of the AI-PRISM components (cobots, AGVs, sensors, people, tools) will require a high-performance communication network to ensure their reliable and real-time operation and integration. The industry relies on classic technologies and architectures that are not flexible enough to enable these new Industry 4.0 needs, where wireless technologies and mobility requirements are more present day by day. This technological layer enables a robust, real-time and secure integration between all the AI-PRISM components, but with the challenge of providing also the needed flexibility, mobility and scalability. State-of-the-art technologies based on deterministic ethernet, Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT), flexible wireless sensing layers and the integration of SDN in the industry, will be the main drivers.
AI-PRISM IIoT Platform	Edge/Cloud platform to support the deployment of data services, simulation services and ROS Framework. Device management and communication services to facilitate the integration of physical devices in the ambient.
AI-PRISM Data Platform	Data services to support AI-based reasoning. It comprises the AI-PRISM Data Model, the Data Broker, the Repositories, and the Data Management functions.
AI-PRISM Simulation Environment	Software services to run Simulation models representing the collaboration ambient, including robots, industrial equipment, and human agents.
AI-PRISM Ambient Digitalisation Modules	Comprehends software modules to integrate data acquired with the AI-PRISM Ambient sensing infrastructure. The data acquired in the form of 2D visual content and 3D geometrical content will be fused to create textured 3D point clouds

	capturing the environment at a precise time frame. The scene reconstruction will be dynamically updated to account for dynamic agents moving in the environment.
AI-PRISM Human Robot Cooperation Ambient	
AI-PRISM CI/CD Framework for AI-based Solutions	Pipelines and infrastructure to support AI-based development, integration and validation. The tooling and infrastructure required to manage AI-based solutions along their lifecycle, considering design, development, discovery, deployment, training, validation, use, monitoring, and improvement.
AI-PRISM AI-based Perception Enhancing Modules	AI-based modules to enhance perception capabilities. Deep learning models will be developed to process the spatio-temporal reconstruction of the environment to produce high-level features capable to describe workers' actions during their working tasks in order to understand their activities and monitor their health status. The activity understanding will be used to teach robot agents how to mimic human activities and safely collaborate with them in the workplace. The health status monitoring will be used to judge how best to assist in, or replace, current parts of workers' activities, thus improving their conditions. Multi-modal models will be explored to fully account for the different sensor modalities. Recurrent neural networks will be explored to account for the temporal aspect of our input data.
AI-PRISM AI-based Agent Level Reasoning Enhancing Modules	An AI-based module that handles the discrete level reasoning/planning between a single robot system and a user interacting with the system. This system will closely interact with the low-level constraint-based controller and will need to exploit the information from AI-based ambient-level reasoning modules in T4.4.
AI-PRISM AI-based Ambient Level Reasoning Enhancing Modules	AI-based modules to enhance the collaboration of agents in the ambient. It includes models and algorithms to solve problems related to the coordination of humans and robotic agents in the ambient, like task allocation, or optimal routing. It also includes modules to enable the control of operations at the ambient level, monitoring events in the ambient and acting in response (e.g. re-allocating tasks or changing the routing) to ensure performance.
AI-PRISM Human - Machine Interaction (HMI) Modules	Integrate the sensor-modalities used in the project in a probabilistic motion/force model for use during execution using a constraint-based framework, both during the learning phase and during the execution phase
AI-PRISM Programming by Demonstration Environment	Integration of the constraint-based framework eTaSL (task specification language for reactive control of robot systems) in the project middleware. Development of the appropriate drivers for the robot system. Programming-by-demonstration is realized by combining model-based constraints with motion and force information from demonstrations. Task definitions will be composed that are appropriate for the classes of tasks considered in the project. This continuous-level Human Robot Interface (HRI) module will integrate with discrete events from the agent-based reasoning modules.
Social Human-Agent-Robots Teams Collaboration	
AI-PRISM Human Safety Management Procedures	The solution improves the safety in warehouses, and in general in workplaces where there are some risks of incident caused by wrong behavior in particular zones or where there are machines with risk of collision. The AI-PRISM Human Safety Management Procedures allows us to check in real-time way the situation in every part of the plant, and warn supervisors if something dangerous or non-compliant happens. The solution can be integrated with other systems/sources of information (i.e. information on parameters of use and operation of equipment such as temperature, pressure, position, etc.) that appropriately analyzed and correlated could highlight any situations of alarm/danger.
AI-PRISM Open Access Network Portal	
AI-PRISM Network Suite	Service suite composed of a dynamic web-based user interface, an online Digital Twin builder, user access control, digital certification, an interactive training engine, scheduling, and optimization engine

1.3. Identification of Main Stakeholders

As defined in D1.1, the stakeholders are considered to be organisations that may be interested in the project results and will potentially use them. Some of the most relevant stakeholders identified

are the Manufacturing Industry, Digital Tech Providers, Social Innovation Sector, Advocate Ecosystem, Policy Makers, and Society.

The main focus of this deliverable is to complement the reference framework and specifications that compose the architecture of AI-PRISM with information regarding the usage, functional and technical specifications of the Key Technical Results. Thus, this section will define the most relevant profiles among the stakeholders that will be in contact with the components developed in the project. These profiles can be defined as Developers, Product Engineers, System Administrators, and Operators.

- Developers are in charge of planning, coding, testing, and debugging the software components that comprise the project. They often have a strong technical background and are proficient in programming languages and software development technologies.
- Engineers are responsible for ensuring that the project's technical components satisfy the defined requirements and are in accordance with business and engineering standards. They work with the development team to define, test, validate, and prioritize features, as well as to handle technical difficulties and ensure that the product is delivered on time and on budget.
- System Administrators are the personnel in charge of installing, configuring, and maintaining the project's hardware and software infrastructure. They manage system resources, monitor performance, troubleshoot problems, and assure the system's security and dependability.
- Operators are the people who make use of the project's system or software to carry out their daily tasks. End-users, customer service representatives, and other staff who interact with the system on a regular basis may be included. Operators may require training and assistance in order to utilize the system properly and provide feedback to the development team.

1.4. [Definition of User Personas](#)

The description of user personas and their related user stories are detailed in the online documentation: [\[LINK\]](#)

1.5. Glossary

This section contains some definitions that are important to understand the objectives of AI-PRISM and the scope of the different technical results.

Table 2: Glossary

Term	Definition
AI-PRISM component	A technical result of the AI-PRISM project, corresponding to a Key Exploitable Result, identified in the DOA, and described in AI-PRISM Reference Framework.
AI-PRISM ambient	A physical space where humans and robots can collaborate in a secure way thanks to AI-PRISM components.
Real time communications	Exchange of information between robotic systems, humans, and other integrated devices or platforms with guaranteed Quality of Service (QoS), ensuring synchronized and harmonized operations. Real time communications implies that the network infrastructure implements mechanism to ensure the requirements (e.g. end-to-end latency below 1 millisecond) for each communication flow. This communication is imperative to guarantee safety, optimize collaborative tasks, and adapt to dynamic environments or changes, allowing both human workers and robots to respond immediately to each other's actions or any unforeseen situations.
Reactive Robot Control	The instantaneous motion of the robot is only partially defined by offline specified targets because, during the execution of the motion, the robot's target is adapted based on online sensor feedback. That reactivity holds for both the continuous and discrete aspects of the robot control.
AI-PRISM modules	An independent software component developed in AI-PRISM that is designed to provide specific functionalities in a collaboration ambient for specific use cases, and that can be discovered, selected, and installed in an AI-PRISM ambient.
Agent	AI-PRISM module designed to autonomously determine the subsequent action or sequence of actions for a robotic system.
Human worker	Individual employees working within the AI-PRISM ambient who are responsible for performing a variety of tasks (manual work, technical tasks, supervision), possibly in collaboration with robot agents. An example of human worker could be a manufacturing operator.

2. Reference Architecture

This section provides a high-level abstract description of AI-PRISM.

2.1. Reference Architecture Overview

Figure 2: AI-PRISM Reference Architecture

The AI-PRISM RA is a representation of the AI-PRISM system focused on the implementation and structure of the AI-PRISM system. It frames the technologies needed to implement the AI-PRISM components and their internal communications. Therefore, it describes the general architecture of the AI-PRISM system, its structure, the distribution of the key technical results across this structure, and the topology by which they are interconnected. Figure 2: AI-PRISM Reference Architecture depicts the AI-PRISM RA, showing the technical structure of AI-PRISM.

The AI-PRISM RA is based on standard-based reference architectures and reference models. [3] and [4] describe and align prominent reference architectures and reference models for Industry 4.0 cyber-physical systems. Software architectures are more than frameworks for execution of functions and exchange of data: the more important aspects deal with **how** components in the system have to behave and adapt their behaviour to that of other components; in this context, several architectural patterns and insights have matured during the last 50 years, of which most have not been integrated into robotic systems. [5] describes many architectural patterns - conceptualization of essential features of a system implementation in a way that is easy to understand by stakeholders - that are

relevant for complex robotic systems and, most notably, for distributed systems, where the implicit assumption of **exactly once delivery** of data does hold in practice when combined with **low latency**.

The overall architecture in Figure 2: AI-PRISM Reference Architecture applies a high-level, simplified, and abstracted view of the AI-PRISM system, providing an initial architectural reference for technical partners, which can be refined and improved upon without holding back or restraining any design consideration during the definition of the system. The AI-PRISM RA is based on the Industrial Internet Reference Architecture (IIRA¹) three-tier architecture pattern, which is a multi-tiered architecture pattern which comprises the edge, platform, and enterprise tiers, and three networks, the proximity network, the access network, and the service network. These concepts are adapted to the AI-PRISM vision in the AI-PRISM RA, which divides the system into 3 primary zones or tiers, namely the device tier, the fog tier, and the device tier. The following subsections provide a brief overview of each of the tiers identified in the AI-PRISM RA.

2.1.1. Edge Tier

The device tier groups all the different devices in the ambient, including sensors, robots, and other manufacturing equipment, collectively referred to as edge devices. The hardware specifications of the sensing infrastructure and the robot hardware vary depending on the specific use cases, however, there is a minimum configuration and specifications common to all instances of AI-PRISM. The AI-PRISM RA device tier differentiates the devices required to sense the collaborative ambient and the humans in the ambient (**Ambient and Human Sensing Infrastructure**, described in section 3.1) from the hardware (**AI-PRISM Base Hardware**, described in **section 3.2** and software components on-board robotic agents (**AI-PRISM ROS Framework**, described in **section 4.1**), and the industrial control systems which are integrated through the AI-PRISM Data Platform Services (**section AI-PRISM Data Platform (DS)**). The edge tier also differentiates the robot agents in the ambient that will use the AI-PRISM base hardware and ROS network from other robots in the collaborative ambient that may use a different hardware and/or operating system. Moreover, the AI-PRISM considers sensors, robots, and other industrial devices in a generic way. The specific characteristics of this tier will vary significantly depending on the specific use cases. Defining the specific sensors or controllers is out of the scope of the AI-PRISM RA.

2.1.2. Ambient Network

The ambient network connects the edge devices and provides real-time communication support between these edge devices and AI-PRISM software modules running in the fog tier. Edge devices

¹ <https://www.iiconsortium.org/iira/>

will be typically connected to a bridge or gateway module, which is a software module that bridges a device or a cluster of devices to the data services in the AI-PRISM Data Platform Services layer. This bridge modules can be executed either at the edge tier (e.g. a data bridge device on board the robot that interconnects the systems on board the robot with the AI-PRISM Data Platform), or at the fog tier (e.g. a southbound communication module that collects data and sends actuation commands to edge devices using communication protocols supported by those devices). The network functions providing real-time communications capabilities are executed in the SDN / NFV (Network Functions Virtualization) Network Infrastructure, which is further described in section **SDN / NFV Network Infrastructure**.

2.1.3. Fog Tier

The fog tier groups the AI-PRISM components that are deployed between the edge tier and the cloud tier. The fog tier components are deployed in a fog cluster which is managed by the end-user organisation (there is normally one cluster per user organisation location). The fog cluster is controlled by the cluster control function of the AI-PRISM IIoT Platform described in section **4.2** and is divided into the following layers or sub-zones.

- 1. AI-PRISM Data Platform Services.** Service layer providing data storage and streaming services for data collected from edge devices in the ambient. The AI-PRISM Data Platform Services are described in section **AI-PRISM CI/CD Framework (CD)**.
- 2. Simulation Modules.** AI-PRISM modules (see glossary or section 3.4 for a more precise definition) to simulate the behaviour of human, robots, or equipment in the ambient.
- 3. Perception Modules.** AI-PRISM modules enhancing the perception capabilities of agents in the collaboration ambient.
- 4. Reasoning Modules.** AI-PRISM modules enhancing the reasoning capabilities of agents in the collaboration ambient.
- 5. Collaboration Modules.** AI-PRISM modules ensuring safe interactions between human and robot agents in the ambient, as well as secure remote access to enable open access to local functions.

2.1.4. Cloud Tier

The cloud tier groups the components that enable Continuous Integration and Continuous Deployment (CI/CD) of solutions (AI-PRISM CI/CD Services), and the components that enable open access to AI-PRISM equipment to external collaborators (AI-PRISM Collaboration Network Services). These components are deployed in the **cloud cluster** in separate sub-zones. Normally, there will be only an instance of the cloud cluster providing these services for all AI-PRISM use cases.

Subsequent sections of this document provide a technical description of the AI-PRISM components, including interfaces, main functions, and important procedures for the management of their lifecycle.

3. Networks and Equipment

This section provides the baseline technical specifications for the different networks and equipment components identified in the AI-PRISM RA.

3.1. [AI-PRISM Ambient and Human Sensing Infrastructure](#)

The AI-PRISM Ambient and Human Sensing Infrastructure consists of sensing equipment to sense the collaboration ambient and the equipment, agents, and other elements in the ambient (robots, humans, obstacles, tools, etc.).

WSN and sensing devices, together with the Internet of Things (IoT) paradigm, constitute the foundation of the AI-PRISM project since they represent the main way through which our system can sense the physical world. In this sense, the IoT is defined as a paradigm in which internet connectivity and computing capability extend to real-world objects, devices, and sensors [6]. AI-PRISM adopts this IoT paradigm, where sensors continuously measure physical events in the collaboration ambient then collected data is transferred via the SDN Network Infrastructure to the AI-PRISM Data Platform Services which enables the creation of digital models of the world, and the development of enhanced perception and reasoning capabilities based on the digital models available.

3.1.1. Baseline Technical Specifications

A collection of distributed and calibrated sensors will be installed in the working environment to enable two core AI-PRISM modules: (i) Ambient Digitalization (AD), which will acquire the content of the scene in digital form, and (ii) Perception Enhancing (PE), which will process the digital representation of the scene content to accomplish the task at hand.

Figure 3. Ambient Sensing Infrastructure

The collection of sensors will contain both mobile (i.e., wearable, robot mounted) and environmental (e.g. fixed onto walls, ceiling) sensors to acquire information of the workplace and the components acting in it (e.g. human workers, robotic agents, obstacles, and tools) under different view-points, reducing occlusions and disambiguating clutter.

Different types of sensors will be considered to capture complementary information. In this version of the specifications, we hypothesize that Red Green Blue (RGB) and depth sensors will be used by default for all the use cases to identify agents in the workplace. Optional sensors like thermal or infrared sensors will be employed where needed. The architectural characteristics of the sensor network are use-case dependent, and this section includes some initial suggestions that may change in future releases of the document.

To record and map the whole workspace, any piece of equipment composed of a camera and/or a depth sensor would be suitable for the task as long as it has an acceptable frame-rate and an available controller compatible with ROS. It would be recommendable using one or several **Intel RealSense Camera**², which, alone, produce RGB-D data, and can provide stereo vision. The more cameras we add to a workspace, the more reliable the data becomes.

Different cameras and sensors can be exploited as long as they are properly calibrated and can have its data merged using already existing ROS algorithms. We do not have to stick to RGB-D devices, alternatively, we can use separate RGB cameras and depth sensors can be used instead.

Automated sensor health and (re)calibration algorithms will be implemented to create a rich network of signals that are interrelated in the same reference system. Based on this information, the goal of

² <https://www.intelrealsense.com/stereo-depth/>

the AD module is to merge the information captured by the sensors, collected from multiple viewpoints and different modalities, to create a 4D representation of the working environment containing its 3D reconstruction at different time frames (time regarded as the fourth dimension). The reconstruction will be represented as a point cloud, whose points are associated with 3D coordinates and additional meta information (e.g. RGB colour, temperature, infrared radiation) if available.

The goal of the PE module is to process the 4D representation of the environment using machine learning algorithms to produce high-level features capable to solve different tasks, including: (i) monitoring the activities of human workers and robotic agents cooperating in the same environment, (ii) monitoring human workers health status, (iii) understanding which activity is being carried out by human workers or robotic agents, (iv) teaching a robotic agent how to mimic the sequence of actions a human worker carries out to accomplish a work task, and (v) generating alerts when predicting the presence of obstacles/people.

Both AD and PE module are described in detail in **section AI-PRISM Ambient Digitalisation Modules (AD)** and **AI-PRISM AI-based Perception Enhancing Modules (PE)** respectively.

3.2. AI-PRISM Base Hardware

As described in the Reference Architecture, the AI-PRISM Base Hardware is the hardware that will host the execution of the AI-PRISM software on-board the robot, not running in the fog cluster. AI-PRISM is a distributed system [7], in the sense that software modules can be executed on-board each of the robots in the ambient, and also in other tiers, primarily the fog tier, as will be further elaborated below and in **section 3.4**. Moreover, in AI-PRISM, each of the instances of the AI-PRISM base hardware in a given ambient is considered an edge device. The fog cluster will host the AI-PRISM Data Platform Services, including device management functions to manage edge devices, and the SDN / NFV Network Infrastructure provides real-time communications support between software components distributed in edge devices and the fog tier. The concepts of edge computing and fog computing are strongly interlinked and for the sake of clarity, this section provides a brief description in the context of AI-PRISM.

Edge computing extends the processing power of IoT devices, using hardware that is installed physically close and directly connected to the device [8]. Similarly, fog computing is defined as a horizontal system-level architecture that distributes computing in the close vicinity of the device, along the path to the cloud [8]. From these definitions, the AI-PRISM Base Hardware is the hardware physically installed on-board the robot, directly connected to the robot system, and the fog cluster spans the hardware components on-board the robot for edge computing, plus any additional hardware required to support the software components deployed in the fog tier (between the AI-

PRISM hardware and the cloud), connected to the AI-PRISM base hardware through the SDN / NFV Network infrastructure.

Figure 4: Fog computing architecture

Figure 4 shows an example of such a fog computing architecture.

3.2.1. Baseline Technical Specifications

As with the ambient sensing technology, the specific hardware installed in the robot is very use case dependent, and there are no hard requirements, bearing in mind that the baseline technical specifications for the fog cluster are described below in **section 3.4.1**, and that the AI-PRISM specifications should be generic and compatible with different robotic solutions. In line with previous sections, this section includes some baseline suggestions that may be updated in future releases.

As specified in the AI-PRISM Ambient Sensing Infrastructure section, the system will require sensors that can provide RGB-Depth data. For short distances in the order of a few meters and where a sensor is attached to a robot, it is recommended to use a Laser Imaging Detection and Ranging (LiDAR) Camera. An example of this could be the **Intel RealSense L515 LiDAR Camera**³ due to its reliability and precision.

³ <https://www.intelrealsense.com/lidar-camera-l515/>

3.3. [SDN / NFV Network Infrastructure](#)

The AI-PRISM network infrastructure layer will enable interoperable communication among sensors, the AI-PRISM Data Platform, edge devices, and AI-PRISM software components. This layer has the challenge of guaranteeing Quality of Service (QoS) and flexibility simultaneously in order to provide a robust but flexible communication infrastructure. For this, the key enablers are robust industrial IoT-based technologies and the integration of software-defined networks in the industry. In this version of the document, the network infrastructure is based on a SDN paradigm [9].

The idea behind SDN is to create a centralized entity that has a global view of the network, even over multiple network technologies (e.g. Time Sensitive Networks (TSN), Ethernet, Wi-Fi, or IEEE 802.15.4 networks). The global knowledge obtained in this entity allows for optimizing decisions that guarantee the end-to-end quality of service.

This centralized entity is the SDN controller, which can manage multiple network technologies using their respective southbound protocol, allows configuring the low-level behaviour of each device. This simplifies the development of applications and services in the fog because the SDN controller offers high-level APIs that connect applications with multiple network technologies without the need for them to know how to perform the low-level configuration. The foreseen advantages of this infrastructure can be summarized as follows:

- Centralization of network management
- Routing and network optimization
- Network monitoring and adaptation to changes
- Scheduled usage of the wireless medium
- On-demand resource request and allocation
- Isolation and prioritization of traffic flows
- End-to-end QoS management

3.3.1. Baseline Technical Specifications

From a technical level, the main objective is to implement a network architecture that enables robust, real-time, and secure integration between all AI-PRISM components, but with the challenge of providing QoS, flexibility, mobility, and scalability. Also integrate a Software Defined Wireless Sensor Network [10], which is a highly deterministic system that guarantees industrial-level requirements using wireless communication technologies developed by ITI, the leader of the development of the SDN/NFV Network Infrastructure. As highlighted in Figure 5, this infrastructure is the main enabler to achieving real-time communications in AI-PRISM. It has a stack of protocols that allow centralized control of all processes in the nodes (e.g. Medium Access Control - MAC, Routing, QoS, Application).

This as mentioned above is based on the SDN paradigm, which manages networks by separating the control plane and the data plane. The control plane is entirely software-controlled, where a centralized agent, in this case, an SDN controller, makes decisions to configure resources and rules in the nodes. The data or forwarding plane are made up of the nodes, which operate in plug-and-play mode, as the controller sends each node all the necessary instructions to achieve maximum performance. In addition, the SDN controller is used as an integration point for the physical network infrastructure and the application that collects the network information and requests network reconfiguration. For that, use a specific protocol for each network technology, for example, OpenFlow for wired SDN network, NetFlow for TSN, and even non-standard protocols such as SDN WISE for WSN.

Figure 5: AI-PRISM Real Time Communications Network

On the bottom layer, this component will focus on the communication technologies to develop, integrate, and provide a real-time communications infrastructure, both wired and wireless, as the basis for supporting the convergence of Information Technology (IT) and Operational Technology (OT) traffic. This architecture will enable robust, real-time, and secure communications in the distributed AI-PRISM system, but with the challenge of providing the needed flexibility, mobility, and scalability for the proposed scenarios. Robust technologies based on IIoT, a flexible wireless sensing layer, and the integration of software-defined networks in the industry will be the main drivers.

On the top layer, the SDN Controller will provide protocols such as MQTT, KAFKA, and a management API so that the AI-PRISM Data Platform can define and develop all the functionality AI-PRISM Data Model, the AI-PRISM data platform, Application Programming Information (APIs)

offering access to data resources (e.g. topics of the data broker and records of repositories), data management functions (filtering, normalization, missing data), and device management functions on top of this communication infrastructure. ARTEMIS⁴ is the candidate solution identified to implement these functions, which will be further elaborated in **section AI-PRISM Data Platform (DS)** in future releases of this document.

3.4. Fog Cluster

As indicated above, the concept of using remote infrastructure to perform the computations of IoT data is called cloud computing and it is widely used to perform integration and sharing of data and resources between different systems to optimize the effectiveness of utilization of these shared systems.

Although cloud computing provides special services for WSN which allow remote sensing and monitoring over the Internet, the cloud performance is constrained by the time it takes to share the data between devices, as it can be inferred from the following simple equation:

$$\text{Latency} = \text{Time from device to cloud} + \text{Time data analysis} + \text{Time from cloud to device}$$

This yields that long delays in device-cloud communications can render specific use case real-time requirements hard or even impossible to meet.

The idea behind using a Fog Computing Cluster or Fog Cluster for short, is to make an extension of the cloud, in order to effectively reduce the latency by placing the services for data processing nearer to the objects that generate IoT information data [8]. The concept of fog computing will not eliminate the cloud technology, but instead, it should be considered as an extension of it since it has its same roles.

In the context of AI-PRISM, as described above in section 2.1, the AI-PRISM cloud services provide services to facilitate the installation and management of AI-PRISM modules in local clusters managed by the end users, and services to enable collaboration with other stakeholders.

This way, this Fog Cluster can be considered as the hardware infrastructure supporting the deployment of the AI-PRISM IIoT Platform: A highly virtualized platform that performs computation, storage, as well as networking services between the network edge devices and the cloud tier. It will communicate with all the devices within a physical space, and may act as a central node for

⁴ <https://www.wings-ict-solutions.eu/artemis/>

expensive computations that require a fast response. It can also act as a translator node that will treat and filter data coming from the edge devices in order to send to the cloud more relevant data for it to be computed or stored. The AI-PRISM IIoT Platform is based on Kubernetes⁵, and is described in **section AI-PRISM Runtime**.

As stated before, the Fog Cluster acts as a mid-point between the Cloud and the end devices. Since the bottleneck of this design dwells around the connectivity between the cloud and the Fog cluster, as well as our ability to treat the data gathered by the end devices, it is imperative to process data at the lowest possible level. For example, if a particular system relies on knowing the position of a particular object calculated from the data of the 3D point cloud acquired from several sensors, it would be wise (if possible) to compute this position at the acquiring unit itself. Doing so reduces the data flow between devices and reduces the computational stress on the upper units. In other words, we should try to avoid as much as possible communication with the cloud, by pre-treating the data at lower levels.

3.4.1. Baseline Technical Specifications

The software modules that will be deployed in the fog cluster require graphic acceleration (use of graphics processing units to enhance the computational capabilities in the fog cluster). As an example of computing devices with graphic acceleration that could be used in the fog cluster are the NVIDIA **Jetson Nano**⁶ and the **Jetson Orin**⁷ embedded boards.

The Jetson Nano embedded board can be installed on-board the end devices. It has a decent processing power and graphical acceleration⁸. It also supports the installation of the runtime environments considered and described in the next sections. Additionally, it offers several options regarding Input / Output (I/O) ports to use and therefore can be used to control a wide variety of hardware components.

Similarly, the Jetson Orin board can be used as a central node to provide additional computational resources in the fog tier. The Jetson Orin is the most powerful commercial board in terms of processing power and also it has graphical acceleration. This board also provides compatibility with Kubernetes containers and excels at network communication speed. The main idea is that the Jetson Orin board acts like a central coordination unit in each workstation, commanding each Jetson Nano

⁵ <https://kubernetes.io/en/>

⁶ <https://developer.nvidia.com/embedded/jetson-nano-developer-kit>

⁷ <https://www.nvidia.com/en-us/autonomous-machines/embedded-systems/jetson-orin/>

⁸ <https://developer.nvidia.com/embedded/jetson-benchmarks>

board which would act like a kind of intermediary between the central coordination unit and each end device.

3.5. Cloud Cluster

The Cloud Cluster is as described above, the infrastructure used for cloud computing consisting of a set of machines hosted in the cloud for running the services that are not sensitive to latency, or that need to be placed in the cloud to enable effective communications between remote connections. These services are identified in the reference architecture as the AI-PRISM Continuous Integration and Continuous Deployment (CI/CD) services, which are the services that allow streamlining the deployment of AI-PRISM ambient, and the AI-PRISM Collaboration Network Services that enable remote access to open pilots.

3.5.1. Baseline Technical Specifications

The cloud cluster is not a key technical result of AI-PRISM, but rather, the additional infrastructure necessary to enable key collaborative features of AI-PRISM. As such, partners involved in the development and provisioning of the software components hosted in the cloud can select the most suitable alternative to optimize resources (e.g. machines in a data centre, a virtual data centre, a managed containerization cluster, managed services, or a combination of these options).

4. Runtime Environments

4.1. AI-PRISM ROS Framework

ROS (Robot Operating System) is an open-source software meant to help build robot applications, ranging from drivers to state-of-the-art algorithms, and includes powerful developer tools. Currently, it is not only used in the field of robotics, but also in a wide range of sectors and applications due to its simplicity of use and its excellence in matter of communication between applications and systems.

As depicted in the Reference Architecture Overview section, the AI-PRISM ROS Framework will be deployed in the robot devices in the device tier, but it is necessary to consider at this stage interactions with other robotic applications for two reasons. First, ROS might not be compatible with e.g. real-time requirements on specific use cases, so it is wise to keep the reference architecture open to non-ROS architectures until the use case requirements are fully defined. Second, AI-PRISM needs to be able to integrate with robots that are already installed in the collaboration workspace, and in any case implement mechanism to integrate with as many robot architectures as possible to increase the potential impact of the technical results.

Regarding real time communications, other non-ROS architectures can be found, such as OROCOS which excels in its real-time control, OpenRDK, OpenRTM or YARP which was intended for

humanoid robotics. Nonetheless, ROS not only provides us with a standardised base for robot application development but is also supported by an extensive and growing community making it the currently preferred tool by developers and industries. In parallel with ROS, we can find other initiatives such as ROS2 or ROS Industrial which solve and improve the ROS lacking capabilities, such as real-time control, and promote its integration in the industry. As for navigation ROS provides off-the-self, ready-to-use capabilities like Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM) and Adaptive Monte Carlo Localization (AMCL) and is compatible with a high number of open source modules, as well as tools for debugging, visualisation, and simulation. For these reasons, ROS is identified in the DOA and in this deliverable as the primary robotic framework. The next sections include some important details of the ROS architecture and ROS version to be used.

4.1.1. ROS Architecture

The ROS 2 has a distributed real-time system architecture. Sensors in robots, motion controllers, detection algorithms, artificial intelligence algorithms, navigation algorithms, etc. are all components (called nodes) of this distributed architecture.

The DDS (Data Distribution Service) middleware selected with ROS 2 for data exchange enables these components to communicate with each other in a distributed environment.

Distributed applications are designed as units known as nodes. All nodes in the system can be run on a single computer or they can be distributed and run across multiple computers.

Nodes communicate with each other via Topics, Services and Actions.

The **topic**-based communication uses a publish-subscribe architecture⁹ where the data produced and published by a node is subscribed by one or more nodes.

Service calls use a remote request-response approach from an application to another.

Actions are an approach used for long service calls, where a node not only makes a request and waits for a response, but can also receive a status via intermediate results.

4.1.2. ROS Version

ROS1 was designed with a couple of characteristics in mind: It was intended to control a single robot, no real time requirements where needed, an excellent connectivity between nodes even using different network types, etc.

⁹ http://wiki.ros.org/ROS/Concepts#ROS_Computation_Graph_Level

ROS 1 fulfilled these requirements very well and it became much more robust than the designers initially intended. However, it still has some limitations which ROS2 tries to address.

ROS2 was implemented to fulfil the following: Standardize an environment to work with Multi-Robot Systems, control and communication using Embedded Systems (Raspberry Pi, Arduino, etc.), facilitate the creation of patterns and templates for building and structuring systems while keeping flexibility, use safer communication protocols to avoid any potential risk of data leakages, etc.

ROS1, added a lot of Open Source unique libraries which have proven to be particularly useful when programming robots and configuration applications. In the early stages of ROS2, a lot of the libraries did not have ROS2 compatibility. This resulted in having to run environments with both ROS1 and ROS2 frameworks, and using bridges to communicate with both, resulting into losing some of those interesting features that could only be used when running singularly. The current reality is that every day, more and more of these useful open-source libraries are, not only porting their libraries to ROS2, but also stop updating them for ROS1. In fact, it should be emphasized that support for ROS ends on May the 1st of 2025, before the end date of the AI-PRISM project.

Hence, it is imperative for the project to use ROS2, since using ROS1 would translate into a degenerative obsolescence.

ROS2 also includes the following features: Zeroconf, Protocol Buffers, Zero Message Queues (MQ) (and other message queues), Redis, Web Sockets, monitorisation of ROS2 applications, multi-platform compatibility between Linux, MacOS and Windows systems, and Data Distribution Service (DDS). AI-PRISM AI-based Perception Enhancing Modules

This DDS is a publish-subscribe transport model that replaces the communication method used in ROS1. The way it works is similar to the ROS1 services, which make a request to send a message and wait for a response. This method which allows the communication between two nodes without the need for a centralized program (like the ROS1 Master), making the communication more robust and flexible.

Another interesting feature is the fact that although ROS1 can be deployed in all, Linux, MacOS and Windows, only ROS2, allows multi-platform communication, between different systems.

More particularly, we are going to use ROS2 Humble, since the rest of ROS2 versions are about to lose their support.

4.2. [AI-PRISM Runtime](#)

As described above, ROS provides the runtime environment for the different modules that will be deployed in the device tier. In a similar way, the AI-PRISM Runtime provides a runtime for the

services to be deployed in the Fog Cluster. The AI-PRISM Runtime integrates a set of components that collectively allow system administrators to browse, select, deploy, monitor, update, and scale AI-PRISM services running in the fog cluster. The AI-PRISM Runtime is based on Kubernetes, which is an open-source system for automating deployment, scaling, and management of containerized applications, and is becoming the de-facto operating system for cloud-based applications. In the Kubernetes architecture, containerized applications run on nodes, which are either virtual or physical machines conforming the cluster. The services of the control plane are handled by the master node(s) and the main functionality is described as follows:

- **API Server:** Provides an internal and external programming interface to manage containerized applications across worker (non-master) nodes (workloads, networks, resources), exposing scheduling and controller functions.
- **Scheduler:** Monitors resources used on each node and balances workloads based on the constraints (resource requirements, resource availability, or other constraints) defined for the deployment of applications.
- **Controller:** Ensures that the actual cluster state is in accordance with the desired state.

Figure 6: IIoT Platform inner architecture

From this perspective, the services, and modules deployable in the Fog Cluster (either reasoning modules, perception modules, Simulation modules, collaboration modules, or AI-PRISM Data Platform services) are Kubernetes applications, packaged in a distributable format and available in an application registry in the AI-PRISM CI/CD Framework. The cluster management service gathers additional Kubernetes cluster management services to facilitate the administration of the cluster, allowing administrator users to browse the application registry, select an application, and install it. It

also gathers services to monitor the status of installed applications. The open-source tool Rancher¹⁰ provides services and management user interfaces to download and install Kubernetes applications from remote catalogues, and to monitor the health and status of the cluster. Lens¹¹ is another open-source Kubernetes management software providing advanced status monitoring and control dashboards to manage Kubernetes clusters.

As mentioned above, it is envisioned that the reasoning, perception, and simulation modules require graphic acceleration. This requirement has already been factored in the specifications of the fog cluster hardware, and consequently, the Kubernetes configuration needs to provide support for graphic acceleration in worker nodes.

4.2.1. Workload placement

Based on the definitions provided, there are different options available to balance the workloads of the different AI-PRISM software modules. The leader of each solution should decide which workloads will be placed in the device tier, running in the native AI-PRISM ROS Framework, and which workloads should be placed in the fog tier managed as Kubernetes applications. It is important to note that ROS2 can also be containerized, deployed, and managed as Kubernetes, so that the leader of each AI-PRISM software modules can decide which parts of the Kubernetes application run in the ROS2 network and which ones run in a different network. At this reporting period (M12), the reference architecture is defined to be flexible enough to accommodate different design alternatives to adapt to different use case scenarios.

5. Software Components

5.1. AI-PRISM ROS Framework (RF)

The ROS Framework acts as a nexus between all the different devices and modules required to command a robot. Ranging from the controller that gathers data, to the controller that conducts the robot, including any modules involved in tasks in between, data treatment, path planning, AI algorithms, etc.

¹⁰ <https://www.rancher.com/>

¹¹ <https://k8slens.dev/>

5.1.1. Usage Models and Mock-ups

5.1.1.1. Usage Models

The following diagrams display the main functionalities of the ROS Framework.

One of the most useful utilities of ROS is its capacity of exchanging messages between Nodes in a simple way.

We can find three types of interactions between Nodes (programs) depending on the nature of the interaction, depending on whether sending a message expects a response, or, in case the message triggers a long process, if feedback is expected while executing the message.

The first and most simple of these interactions, is the Publish-Subscribe interaction, where a Node, simply publishes messages to a Topic, and any other Node subscribed to said Topic receives a copy of said message, as you can see depicted in Figure 7:

Figure 7 ROS Publish-Subscribe Usage Model

The second kind of interaction is the Client-Server interaction, where a Node Client sends a request to a Node Server and this Server Node sends back a reply, as you can see depicted in Figure 8:

Figure 8 ROS Server-Client Usage Model

Finally, the most complex of all interactions is action interaction. This interaction is meant for long processes where just receiving a reply wouldn't be enough. The action interaction is like a combination of the Publish-Subscriber and the Client-Service interactions since it relies on both.

As is seen in Figure 9, the Node requesting an action needs to first make a service call to the action server through the goal service. The action server will reply whether the goal was successfully set or not. Then the action client proceeds by sending a server call to the action client through the response server. The action server will start streaming the status of the given task/action through the "current state topic". Once the action has finished (successfully or unsuccessfully), the action server will reply to the action client whether the action execution finished successfully or not.

Figure 9 ROS Action Usage Model

ROS enables communications between devices and is prepared to interact with slow reacting devices (e.g. a robot). ROS is very convenient as a communication middleware between different pieces of software.

5.1.1.2. Mock-ups

Mock-ups and more information related to the component's usage can be found in the online documentation [\[LINK\]](#).

5.1.2. Functional Specifications

The working principle is rather simple, and it has already been defined before in “*D2.1 – Reference Framework and Specifications and Specifications (I)*”, section “*4.1. AI-PRISM ROS Framework*”. The ROS Framework holds the nodes or programs capable of commanding the robot, as well of any piece of equipment that can be connected to it. If the data needs to be evaluated, it can also be done inside the ROS environment. Any piece of useful data can be sent to the cloud. Alternatively, ROS can gather any information stored in the cloud. Finally, with all this data, ROS will command the robot into performing its duties, no matter if the specific task is collaborative or not.

ROS2 uses a Fast DDS as a middleware technology to enable communication between different components in a distributed robotic system. The Fast DDS provides an abstraction layer, which allows different components to communicate regardless of their underlying implementation details.

The server plays a crucial role in facilitating this communication.

Overall, the Fast DDS server acts as a bridge between publishers and subscribers in a ROS2 system. It manages topic discovery, facilitates data transmission, enforces QoS settings, and provides a standardized communication layer for components to interact with each other effectively.

This DDS server is in charge of receiving the details and information of a Node when this one is initialized. The server repeats the information to the rest of the Nodes, so each Node is aware of all the rest. This system replaces the old discovery system where each Node had to send separately its identity to all the other nodes.

Figure 10 ROS2 DDS Discovery Server Working Diagram

More information related to the component's functional specifications can be found in the online documentation [\[LINK\]](#).

5.1.3. Technical Specifications

The software architecture will have to guarantee the integration of several control devices (from both, software and hardware elements) and a proper synchronization between the different modules ((collaborative) robots, planners, vision systems, data management, cloud, collaborative manipulator, etc...).

To ensure these requirements, the software control architecture will include the following specifications:

- **ROS:** The external control will be developed using the environment provided by ROS.

- **Real-Time:** Those control nodes, critical for the management and regulation of the control loops should be executed under Soft Real Time requirements.
- **Modularity:** All the implementations should allow enabling and disabling specific modules depending on the needs of a particular operation.
- **Integration and compatibility:** Different technologies, hardware devices and programming languages will be used, therefore they should be able to be integrated in an agile and easy way. Therefore, there should not exist any particular hardware dependencies and the developed software should be easy to deploy.
- **Programming:** The control system will be developed using different programming languages, highlighting the use of C++ and Python since those are the only allowed languages compatible with ROS. The necessity of using additional programming languages will require additional Frameworks outside ROS.
- **Cloud connection:** The ROS framework will require a connection with a cloud server for storing and computing capabilities.

More information related to the component's technical specifications can be found in the online documentation [[LINK](#)].

5.2. [AI-PRISM Base Framework \(BH\)](#)

ROS2 has been widely mentioned in “D2.1 – Reference Framework and Specifications and Specifications (I)”, section “4.1. AI-PRISM ROS Framework” as the best choice for the project as it can be containerized in order to simplify its deployment.

Independent of how AI-PRISM will be deployed, in this section are defined the different modules that each environment should use.

5.2.1. Usage Models and Mock-ups

5.2.1.1. Usage Models

In Figure 11 we identify the ROS Framework. The ROS Framework will include all the modules necessary to control the robot, as well as the controllers related with any piece of hardware involved in the project at the plant level. These modules have a certain degree of complexity and, therefore, only an experienced ROS developer should temper with the ROS Framework file system.

The ROS Framework provides us with the advantage that any module can subscribe and publish to any other, and as such, all modules have access to any data if it requires it. The ROS Framework

will gather any incoming data from the optical sensors (or any other sensor that we might require) and will provide it to any module that might need that data.

With this advantage in mind, we can run in parallel a great variety of tasks, such as the robot controller, SLAM, computer vision algorithms, etc. as we can see in Figure 11.

ROS will command the robot with any motion it might have to perform, and it will collect and treat any useful data gathered from the sensors.

Any worker performing any particular collaborative task or helping with robot training might be generating useful training data. This data might be sent to the cloud (not shown on the ROS Framework Usage Model Figure) before or after it has been evaluated, helping with the data treatment process from the very source.

Finally, a technical user could have access to an HMI screen which would provide information about the different physical devices connected to the ROS Network, as well as the running modules within each one of those.

Figure 11 ROS Framework Usage Model

All nodes and packages in common between pilots, will be containerised together inside a Docker image. This Docker image will be called “AI-PRISM ROS Base Framework Image”.

All the other modules and packages will be split into separate and self-sufficient containers, meaning they can be built and executed without the need of any other.

A deployment tool will be implemented to allow the user to easily choose which additional modules for each specific pilot/case he/she would like to choose.

5.2.1.2. Mock-ups

Mock-ups and more information related to component's usage can be found in the online documentation [\[LINK\]](#).

5.2.2. Functional Specifications

- **Planning and navigation:** This node is in charge of computing what the robot should do, ranging from complex decisions such as what particular task to do at a particular moment, to which specific motions the robot should perform from going to position A to position B. It should be discussed if this node should be split into planning and mission manager, or it can be kept as one.
- **Machine Learning:** This node oversees system learning. It ranges from memorizing routines, to understanding the quality of the robots' performed tasks. It should be discussed what exactly this node should learn from. It should also be discussed if it is going to be this node that sends any useful data to the cloud server.
- **SLAM:** This node will recreate the working environment. It should be discussed how to filter transient objects from permanent structures and how and where to store this information.
- **Simulation:** This node is in charge of any prior simulations before any motion is performed. It should be discussed the purpose of this simulations. Will they be used to help the Machine learning node? Or will they work in parallel with the planning and navigation nodes to command the robot?
- **Device Controller:** This will transform the instructions from the planning and navigation nodes into understandable signals to command the robot into performing desired motions.

Figure 12 AI-PRISM ROS Base Framework working diagram

More information related to the component's functional specifications can be found in the online documentation [\[LINK\]](#).

5.2.3. Technical Specifications

As can be seen in Figure 13, the nodes will be split depending on which physical system will be deployed. The nature of this split will be explained further within the section 5.3 AI-PRISM Communication Modules (CM). Nonetheless, it should be remarked that since all nodes will be running within the ROS2 environment, all nodes indistinctly of the physical device they are running or the container they are packaged in will be able to transfer data from one another.

Figure 13 AI-PRISM ROS Base Framework Technical specifications data sharing diagram

More information related to the component's technical specifications can be found in the online documentation [\[LINK\]](#)

5.3. AI-PRISM Communication Modules (CM)

In this section the communication modules will be explained. As stated in section [2. AI-PRISM Base Framework \(BH\)](#), all the modules will be split into different Docker containers. As long as all the containers are present in the same network, Docker containers can communicate between one another if configured accordingly. More details will be provided during the following sections.

5.3.1. Usage Models and Mock-ups

5.3.1.1. Usage Models

Docker is an open-source platform that enables developers to automate the deployment and management of applications within isolated environments, called containers. Containers are encapsulated applications which include all its required dependencies, such as libraries, frameworks, and system tools. Docker allows us to easily deploy and run these containerized applications to run smoothly across computing environments.

As developers, using docker we can package our custom applications as containers. Since Docker provides its own running environment, using it eliminates the "works on my machine" problem by providing a standardized and isolated environment for running applications. Docker utilizes an efficient image sharing mechanism, enabling fast and efficient container creation and distribution.

Docker networks are virtualized networking environments within the Docker platform that allow containers to communicate and connect with each other (see Figure 14). They provide isolated spaces for containers, enabling seamless communication using IP addresses. Docker networks facilitate secure and efficient interactions between containers, whether they are running on the same host or distributed across multiple systems.

Figure 14 Docker network use case diagram

Since we have established that Docker containers can share data between one another, it is also important to define and configure said packages to allow ROS2 nodes to properly communicate between themselves.

While ROS2 eliminates the need for a “centralized master node” for node communication, it is possible to create a Docker container hosting a “ROS_MASTER” for specific use cases. By defining a “ROS_MASTER” inside a Docker container, other Docker containers containing ROS2 nodes can

establish connections with this master container. This setup can be advantageous in our scenario where a centralized coordination point exists (it being the AI-PRISM Base ROS Framework Image). We are declaring this specific container as ROS_MASTER so the other containers can connect to it, but a “ROS Master Node” *per se* will not exist.

The extension of the previous Figure 144 to implement the mentioned ROS_MASTER is depicted in Figure 15:

Figure 15 ROS Master-Slave docker communication structure diagram

5.3.1.2. Mock-ups

As stated in Section [2. AI-PRISM Base Framework \(BH\)](#), an interface will be implemented to easily specify which containers will be deployed on each device.

In the [Mock-ups](#) part of the same section, a mock-up of a graphical interface has been introduced to monitor the status of the devices and the programs running within them. It may be wise to merge the monitor and the deploy capabilities within the same interface, nonetheless it will be discussed and decide in the future how to approach this matter.

Mock-ups and more information related to the component's usage can be found in the online documentation [[LINK](#)].

5.3.2. Functional Specifications

Since there exists a ROS_MASTER container, we must ensure that this container is the first one to be deployed. Docker allows us to use “Docker Composer” filers to precisely define the launching order of each Docker container, the Network each one will be part of and the commands that will be sent to each container on startup, between other functionalities.

This will be useful to specify the role of the ROS_MASTER container and let others have a direct connection with it.

The flowchart depicting the order in which every container will be deployed can be seen in Figure 16:

Figure 16 ROS Master-Slave working diagram

More information related to the component's functional specifications can be found in the online documentation [\[LINK\]](#).

5.3.3. Technical Specifications

In this section we will list the most important containers, and the already existing packages that will populate them.

In the future, this list will keep growing and be updated as the AI-PRISM project goes on. Hand-coded nodes needed to perform required tasks will be defined in the section [2. AI-PRISM Base Framework \(BH\)](#).

Figure 17 depicts the current structure of the 2 different AI-PRISM containers. We will proceed listing them and providing a brief explanation of each one of them:

Figure 17 AI-PRISM Docker Images packages

AI-PRISM Base Docker Image:

- **rosbag2:** A ROS2 package that provides a flexible and efficient way to record, play back, and analyse data from ROS2 topics. It allows users to capture and store sensor data and system state information for later analysis or debugging.
- **urdfdom:** A ROS2 package that provides a C++ library for parsing URDF (Unified Robot Description Format) files. It enables developers to read and manipulate robot models, extracting information about links, joints, and other elements to facilitate robot visualization, planning, and control.
- **orocos_kinematics_dynamics:** A ROS2 package that integrates the Orocos Kinematics and Dynamics Library (KDL). It offers advanced algorithms for solving forward and inverse kinematics problems, as well as dynamic computations for robot manipulators. This package enables accurate modelling and simulation of robot motions and interactions.

- **tf2:** A ROS2 package that provides a transform library for managing coordinate frame transformations. It allows users to track the positions and orientations of multiple objects relative to each other over time. This package is essential for robot perception, navigation, and coordination, enabling seamless integration of sensor data from different frames of reference.
- **robot_state_publisher:** A ROS2 package that publishes the state of a robot model to the tf2 transform tree. It takes a URDF description and joint state information as input and broadcasts the corresponding transforms. This package plays a crucial role in visualizing and controlling robot movements in simulation or on physical robots.
- **moveit:** A ROS2 package that provides a flexible motion planning framework for manipulators and mobile robots. It offers a comprehensive set of tools and algorithms for motion planning, manipulation, and perception. MoveIt simplifies the development of complex robot applications, enabling tasks such as obstacle avoidance, trajectory generation, and grasping.

More information related to the component's technical specifications can be found in the online documentation [[LINK](#)].

5.4. [AI-PRISM Ambient Sensing Infrastructure \(AS\)](#)

The AI-PRISM Ambient Sensing (AS) infrastructure consists of a collection of mobile (i.e. wearable, robot mounted) and environmental (e.g. fixed onto walls, ceiling) sensors that will be used to digitise the workplace and the components acting in it (e.g. human workers, robotic agents, obstacles, and tools). In this deliverable we will focus on a specific sensor type, namely RGBD cameras (e.g. Intel RealSense), but other sensor types such as thermal or infrared sensors can be considered as well. Multiple RGBD cameras from different view-points are used to reduce occlusions.

5.4.1. Usage Models and Mock-ups

5.4.1.1. *Usage Models*

The AS infrastructure consists of a network of sensors and provides a tool for sensing the working environments and actors (e.g. human workers, robotic agents, tools) present in it. The AS system consists of the following modules:

- **Configure sensor network:** Allows the operator to choose which sensors to activate from the list of sensors available through a UI. For example, only environmental sensors can be activated and sensors pointing out of the region of interest can be deactivated.

- **Check sensors health status:** Checks the health status of the selected sensors and sends alert notifications if some sensors are faulty.
- **Calibrate sensors:** Performs the calibration of the healthy sensors so that data acquired with them shares a common reference system.
- **Record:** Starts/ends the recording from each healthy sensor.
- **Send data to Ambient Digitalization:** Sends data to the AI-PRISM Ambient Digitalization modules for real-time processing and stores them in a database to make them available later.

There are two types of human workers interacting with the AS system: the system administrator can interact with all the modules of the system and thus has technical expertise about the system, while the operator can access only the configuration module and has just a basic knowledge about sensor types.

Figure 18: AS Use Case Diagram

More information related to the component's usage can be found in the online documentation [\[LINK\]](#).

5.4.1.2. Mock-ups

This is a backend development component, hence it does not require frontend interfaces.

5.4.2. Functional Specifications

The diagram in Figure 19: AS Functional Block Diagram represents the functional specifications of the AS infrastructure. When data acquisition starts we first check if all the AS sensors are working properly. If one or more sensor is faulty, we raise an alert notification. We then check if healthy sensors are calibrated, otherwise we must perform camera calibration so that data acquired from different sensors will share the same reference frame. Once AS cameras are calibrated, data recording can start. At each time frame, an RGBD sensor stores an RGB image capturing photometric information and a depth (D) image capturing geometric information (distance to the sensor). Both images capture content from a specific view-point. Data is then passed to AI-PRISM Ambient Digitalization (AD) modules for real-time processing and are stored in a database. Storing data in a database will allow experts to annotate them using dedicated software for machine learning training purposes, and will enable software inspection (e.g. performing sanity checks about unexpected software behaviours). Each data acquisition session lasts for several checkpoints, where a checkpoint can be defined either as a specific number of frames or as a time interval. After each checkpoint, we check whether the acquisition should end, otherwise we repeat the procedure described so far. If mobile cameras are used, each frame is a checkpoint because camera calibration should be repeated for each position of the mobile sensors. If only environmental (fixed) cameras are used, it is sufficient to calibrate cameras only once per acquisition, usage session.

Figure 19: AS Functional Block Diagram

More information related to the component's functional specifications can be found in the online documentation [\[LINK\]](#).

5.4.3. Technical Specifications

Figure 20: AS Technical Diagram

The diagram represents the technical specifications of AS and its main technical components.

More information related to the component's technical specifications can be found in the online documentation [[LINK](#)].

5.5. AI-PRISM Real Time Communications Network (RC)

The AI-PRISM Real-Time Communications Network (RC) is a key integrator of multiple technologies based on Software-Defined Networking (SDN) to optimize and manage real-time communications in heterogeneous networks. This comprehensive component includes wired and wireless SDN networks built on the 802.15.4e standard, ensuring seamless integration and efficient communication across various network infrastructures. Additionally, the RC can extend its functionality by incorporating network technologies from other partners, further enhancing its ability to provide a unified and robust platform for managing complex communication environments.

5.5.1. Usage Models and Mock-ups

5.5.1.1. Usage Models

User requests: End-users or applications initiate communication requests, specifying their QoS requirements, such as bandwidth, latency, or priority levels.

Agent communication: Network agents, such as IoT devices, sensors, and routers, relay the user requests and report their current network conditions, including link capacity, utilization, and congestion, to the SDN controller.

SDN controller processing: The SDN controller analyses the user requests and network conditions, considering the QoS requirements and any predefined policies or rules. Based on this analysis, the controller determines the optimal flow configurations and routing paths to meet the QoS demands.

Flow configuration and routing update: The SDN controller communicates the new flow configurations and routing paths to the relevant network agents, instructing them to update their forwarding tables and apply the required changes.

Network agents' execution: update their forwarding tables and implement the new flow configurations and routing paths as directed by the SDN controller.

Monitoring and adjustment: The SDN controller continuously monitors network performance and user demands, adjusting flow configurations and routing paths in real-time to maintain the desired QoS levels and adapt to network changes or fluctuations.

Figure 21. AI-PRISM Software-Defined Network Use Case Diagram

Through this usage model, the AI-PRISM Real-Time Communications Network (RC) component facilitates seamless interactions between diverse agents and the SDN controller, enabling dynamic network management and ensuring optimal QoS for all users and applications.

5.5.1.2. Mock-ups

Mock-ups and more information related to the component's usage can be found in the online documentation [\[LINK\]](#).

5.5.2. Functional Specifications

Centralized SDN Controller: The core of the AI-PRISM RC system is the SDN controller, providing a global and unified network view, enabling real-time resource management and optimization. The controller makes decisions based on network information and enforces policies and actions on network devices.

Network Abstraction Layer: This layer provides an abstract view of the underlying network infrastructure, enabling the controller to handle various network devices and protocols seamlessly.

Controller API: The controller API enables integration with third-party applications and extends the controller's capabilities. Through the API, developers can access network information and control network devices, allowing customized solutions to be developed.

Northbound Interface: The northbound interface exposes network information and control functions to higher-level applications and services.

Southbound Interface: The southbound interface communicates with network devices using standardized protocols such as OpenFlow.

SDN-enabled Network Devices: Network devices such as switches and routers are SDN-compatible and communicate with the controller using standardized protocols like OpenFlow. These devices can be dynamically configured and managed by the SDN controller.

Resource Orchestration Module: This module allocates and optimizes network resources, including bandwidth, routing, and Quality of Service (QoS), ensuring real-time communications meet performance and latency requirements.

Traffic Analysis Module: The traffic analysis module assesses real-time network conditions and traffic trends, providing valuable input to the controller for informed decision-making on resource management and policy implementation.

Figure 22. AI-PRISM Software-Defined Network Functional Block Diagram

More information related to the component's functional specifications can be found in the online documentation [\[LINK\]](#).

5.5.3. Technical Specifications

Centralized SDN Controller: The SDN controller is built on a scalable, distributed software platform that ensures high availability and fault tolerance. The controller utilizes standardized protocols like OpenFlow and NETCONF to communicate with network devices and control traffic flow.

Network Abstraction Layer: The abstraction layer is implemented using object-oriented programming techniques and design patterns, enabling the controller to support different network devices and protocols with minimal code changes.

Controller API: The SDN controller's API is based on REST, allowing easy integration with external applications and systems. The API provides real-time access to network state, device, and routing information and the ability to control and configure network devices.

Northbound Interface: The northbound interface is implemented using standard web protocols (e.g., HTTP/HTTPS) and data formats (e.g., JSON, XML), ensuring compatibility with a wide range of applications and services.

Southbound Interface: The southbound interface supports various standardized protocols such as OpenFlow, NETCONF, and SDN WISE, allowing for seamless communication with multiple network devices.

SDN-enabled Network Devices: Network devices are equipped with SDN-compatible firmware and support standardized protocols for communication with the SDN controller. Devices can be dynamically provisioned and configured based on the policies and actions the controller defines.

Figure 23. AI-PRISM Software-Defined Network Technical Diagram

More information related to the component's technical specifications can be found in the online documentation [[LINK](#)].

5.6. AI-PRISM IIoT Platform (IP)

The Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) Platform component serves as the primary interface for communication, interaction, and real-time data retrieval from IoT devices, robots, simulation modules, reasoning modules, and perception modules. The platform is designed to operate in a Fog Cluster, enabling efficient and rapid processing closer to the data source. It operates in the Fog Tier and focuses on managing the real-time state of these modules and providing access to Northbound interfaces such the collaboration modules.

Key aspects of the IIoT Platform Component include:

Communication Layer: This layer is responsible for secure and efficient communication between the off-site and on-site infrastructure, using MQTT and REST API endpoints for real-time data collection and two-way communication. The communication layer incorporates Sensor, Robot, and Human-Machine Interface (HMI) APIs for translating raw data into semantically interpreted events and states.

Core Layer: The core layer is the main application logic layer, which combines data, events, and states, facilitating two-way interaction with the monitored and controlled IoT devices. This layer synchronizes the entire infrastructure and services using a common event loop and state machine, and it monitors the IIoT platform process through metrics collection and watchdogs for each critical component.

Reasoning Layer: The reasoning layer provides centralized automation rules, transformation services for decision support. This can be used in parallel with specialized reasoning modules deployed in the Fog cluster.

Fog Cluster Control Function: The IIoT Platform supports control over the simulation, perception, reasoning, and collaboration modules within the Fog Cluster via High-level interfaces supported and exposed by the modules. This control function will interact with the core layer, ensuring seamless operation and interaction with the diverse modules in the Fog Cluster.

5.6.1. Usage Models and Mock-ups

5.6.1.1. Usage Models

The UML use case diagram in Figure 24: IP Use Case Diagram includes the following main actors:

Operators: Manages and interact with the IIoT platform and its components.

IIoT Devices (Robots, Sensors and actuators): Communicate with the platform, sending and receiving data.

Simulation Modules: Simulate device behaviour and communicate with the platform.

Reasoning Modules: Provide decision support based on rule-based automation and inference engines.

Fog Cluster Interfaces: Control over the simulation, perception, reasoning, and collaboration modules within the Fog Cluster via High-level interfaces supported and exposed by the modules.

Northbound Interfaces: Integrate with the IIoT platform for task lifecycle management and coordination.

The main use cases are:

Data Ingestion: IIoT devices send real-time data to the platform.

Data Processing: The IIoT platform processes real-time data, transforming raw data into meaningful information and mapping devices to virtual entities.

System Monitoring: The platform monitors the state of IIoT devices and system health.

Data Communication: The platform communicates processed data and commands to IIoT devices and Northbound interfaces.

Reasoning and Decision Support: The reasoning modules use transformed data for decision support.

Fog Cluster control: Support for controlling the Fog Cluster modules.

The IIoT devices and simulation modules interact with the platform by sending real-time data and receiving commands. The reasoning modules use the processed data for decision support, and the Northbound interfaces may use the IIoT Platform high-level APIs for task lifecycle management.

Figure 24: IP Use Case Diagram

More information related to the component's usage can be found in the online documentation [\[LINK\]](#).

5.6.1.2. Mock-ups

This is a backend development component, hence it does not require frontend interfaces.

5.6.2. Functional Specifications

The functional block diagram in Figure 25: IP Functional Block Diagram includes the following main inputs, functional components, and outputs:

Inputs:

- Real-time data from IIoT Devices and Simulation Modules.
- Rules and conditions from Reasoning Modules.

Main Functional Components:

- Communication Layer: Handles data ingestion from IIoT devices and simulation modules.
- Core Layer: Processes the ingested data and monitors system health.
- Reasoning Layer: Provides decision support based on the processed data.

Outputs:

- Processed data sent to IIoT devices, Northbound interfaces, and Reasoning Modules.
- System health status to the System Administrator.

The activity begins with IIoT devices and simulation modules sending real-time data to the platform. The communication layer ingests this data and forwards it to the core layer for processing. The processed data is sent to the reasoning layer, where decision support occurs based on the data and set rules. The processed data is then communicated back to the IIoT devices, Northbound interfaces, and reasoning modules. Operators then may interact with the platform.

Figure 25: IP Functional Block Diagram

More information related to the component's functional specifications can be found in the online documentation [[LINK](#)].

5.6.3. Technical Specifications

The technical diagram in Figure 26: IP Technical Diagram includes the following main components:

MQTT and REST API Endpoints: Facilitate two-way communication between the platform and IIoT devices and simulation modules.

Sensor, Robot, and HMI APIs: Translate raw data into semantically interpreted events and states.

State Machine and Event Loop: Manage the synchronization and coordination of data flow and processing within the platform.

Fog Cluster control: Mapping of Fog Cluster interfaces to virtual entities for control.

Rule-based Automation Engine and Inference Engines: Part of the reasoning layer, they provide decision support based on the processed data.

The MQTT and REST API endpoints facilitate two-way communication, enabling data ingestion from and command dissemination to IIoT devices and simulation modules. The Sensor, Robot, and HMI APIs are part of the communication layer that translate raw data into meaningful information. The core layer uses a state machine and event loop for data flow and processing management. The rule-based automation engine and inference engines in the reasoning layer provide decision support. The processed data is then communicated to the relevant actors through the MQTT and REST API endpoints.

Figure 26: IP Technical Diagram

More information related to the component's technical specifications can be found in the online documentation [\[LINK\]](#).

5.7. AI-PRISM Data Platform (DS)

The Data Platform Component is designed to handle the persistence of data from the IIoT Platform component. This includes data from simulated entities, mapped IoT and Robot devices. The Platform is responsible for making the persisted data available in a batch or streaming manner.

Key aspects of the Data Platform Component include:

Persistence Layer: This layer provides persistence services to all other components. It utilizes relational databases, object and file storage, and time-series databases to support the appropriate data model for different applications.

Data Access Layer: This layer provides external access to the persisted data through REST APIs, Server-Side events, and Message Queues, enabling the streaming of data.

Data Management Layer: This layer is responsible for the management and organization of persisted data. It offers functionality for data cataloguing and data lifecycle management.

The IIoT Platform Component and Data Platform Component, together, offer a comprehensive solution for IIoT data communication, processing, and storage. They interact with each other seamlessly to ensure efficient operation, providing real-time interaction with IoT devices and Robots, and secure data persistence and retrieval.

5.7.1. Usage Models and Mock-ups

5.7.1.1. Usage Models

The UML use case diagram in Figure 27: DS Use Case Diagram includes the following main actors:

System Administrator: Manages and maintains the Data Platform and its components, and monitors system health.

IIoT Platform: Persist data to the platform.

External Systems: Receive raw and processed data from the platform for further action.

The main use cases are:

Data Ingestion: IIoT devices and Simulation Modules send real-time data to the IIoT Platform which are persisted in the Data Platform.

Data Storage: The platform stores the ingested data in appropriate databases.

Data Access: External systems access the stored data either in batch or streaming manner.

The System Administrator oversees the entire operation, managing and maintaining the platform, and ensuring efficient data storage and access. The IIoT devices and simulation modules interact with the platform by sending real-time data. The platform then stores this data in appropriate databases, making it accessible to external systems either in batch or streaming manner.

Figure 27: DS Use Case Diagram

More information related to the component's usage can be found in the online documentation [\[LINK\]](#).

5.7.1.2. Mock-ups

This is a backend development component, hence it does not require frontend interfaces.

5.7.2. Functional Specifications

The functional block diagram in Figure 28: DS Functional Block Diagram includes the following main inputs, functional components, and outputs:

Inputs:

- Real-time data from the IIoT Platform.

Main Functional Components:

- Data Ingestion: Handles data ingestion from the IIoT Platform.
- Data Storage: Stores the ingested data in appropriate databases.
- Data Access: Facilitates data access by external systems.

Outputs:

- Stored data made accessible to External Systems.

The activity begins with IIoT devices and simulation modules sending real-time data to the platform. This data is then stored in appropriate databases. External systems can access the stored data either in a batch or streaming manner.

Figure 28: DS Functional Block Diagram

More information related to the component's functional specifications can be found in the online documentation [\[LINK\]](#).

5.7.3. Technical Specifications

The technical diagram in Figure 29: DS Technical Diagram includes the following main components:

Data Ingestion APIs: Facilitate data ingestion from IIoT devices and simulation modules.

Database Systems: Store the ingested data in appropriate formats.

Data Access APIs: Facilitate data access by external systems.

The Data Ingestion APIs facilitate data ingestion from the IIoT Platform. The ingested data is then stored in the appropriate Database Systems, which could be a mix of relational databases, object storage, and time-series databases. The Data Access APIs facilitate data access by external systems, providing the ability to access data either in batch or streaming manner.

Figure 29: DS Technical Diagram

More information related to the component's technical specifications can be found in the online documentation [[LINK](#)].

5.8. [AI-PRISM Simulation Environment \(SE\)](#)

5.8.1. Usage Models and Mock-ups

5.8.1.1. Usage Models

The simulation platform allows the user to simulate the scenarios of the pilots to test the developed components. This environment provides the user with a tool to optimize their own solutions by applying them in simulations of target scenarios. The following elements describe the main use cases shown Figure 30: Simulation Environment Use Case Diagram.

- **Select Layout:** Through the UI, the system administrator / user of the application will choose the layout to simulate from the catalogue of the available scenarios.
- **Configure:** Once the layout is selected, the scene needs to be configured by adding different agents (e.g., robots, human avatars) in predefined spots marked in the layout. The

administrator configures a basic setup that includes information related to the real agent to simulate. Additionally, some simulation parameters need to be introduced.

- **Save layout:** Not mandatory feature that allows the user to save the current layout with the filled information of the agents.
- **Run simulation:** Executes the simulation and provides the user with production parameters and test the user’s specific tools.

Figure 30: Simulation Environment Use Case Diagram

5.8.1.2. Mock-ups

Mock-ups and more information related to the component's usage can be found in the online documentation [[LINK](#)].

5.8.2. Functional Specifications

The functional specifications in Figure 31. Simulation Environment Functional Diagram represent the flow of the main actions in the Simulation Environment. The activities start with the selection of an agent (e.g. robot, conveyor, human...) from a list of available agents. If an agent is selected, the agent should be configured. The configuration is related to the key features that define the agent previously selected. In this step, the user should introduce the properties that will determine the behaviour of the agent. Following, if the agent has been correctly configured, it can be positioned in the scene. To perform this action, the user must provide the spatial coordinates in which the agent will be located. Once all the agents composing a scene are positioned, the user should decide if the definition of the layout is completed. If the layout is defined, it can be saved, with the option of storing it in the database for later use or directly running the simulation.

Figure 31. Simulation Environment Functional Diagram

More information related to the component's functional specifications can be found in the online documentation [[LINK](#)].

5.8.3. Technical Specifications

The technical specification diagram in Figure 32: Simulation Environment Technical Specifications Diagram represents the architecture of the simulation environment and its main technical components. The Web App module will have a frontend which will provide all the user interfaces needed to complete the actions mentioned in the Use Case and Functional Specifications diagrams. A backend service will be used to handle the information provided in the frontend, retrieve, and save data from the database. Also, send all information to the 3D visualization framework. The Process Database will contain two modules: Process Module Engine, that will register the needs of the production line (i.e., shift production, types of products) and, Resources Module Engine, that will collect the information regarding the available capabilities (i.e., number of machines available, workers). Last, 3D visualization framework will receive the information collected, and display the production line chosen in a 3D realistic environment ready to be simulated.

Figure 32: Simulation Environment Technical Specifications Diagram

More information related to the component's technical specifications can be found in the online documentation [[LINK](#)].

5.9. [AI-PRISM Ambient Digitalisation Modules \(AD\)](#)

The AI-PRISM Ambient Digitalization (AD) module takes as input data acquired by the AS infrastructure and produces as output a digital reconstruction of the working environment and the actors (e.g. human workers, robotic agents, tools) present in it. If RGBD sensors are used together with other types of sensors (e.g. thermal or infrared), the AD module will produce a multimodal representation.

5.9.1. Usage Models and Mock-ups

5.9.1.1. *Usage Models*

The AD module consists of software modules to digitalize the working environment by creating a 4D representation of it consisting of a texturized 3D point cloud for each time frame. AD software modules comprehend:

- A Configuration interface that allows an inexperienced operator to configure the desired sensors network and data type to be recorded.
- **Get RGBD images from Ambient Sensing:** Gets RGBD images from the AI-PRISM Ambient Sensing infrastructure.
- **Synchronize RGBD images:** Checks if the RGBD images are aligned, otherwise perform synchronization through timestamp alignment.
- **Create 3D point clouds:** Given an RGBD image captured from a sensor and its intrinsic parameters it performs depth lifting to get a colored 3D point cloud representation.
- **Perform point cloud registration:** Aligns the 3D point cloud fragments recorded from the different sensors to create a comprehensive digital representation.
- **Send data to Perception Enhancement:** Sends data to the AI-PRISM Perception Enhancement modules for real-time processing and stores them in a database to make them available later.

There are two types of actors interacting with the AD modules: the expert system administrator who develops them, and the inexperienced operator who should just specify the ideal configuration through an interface.

Figure 33: AD Use Case Diagram

More information related to the component's usage can be found in the online documentation [\[LINK\]](#).

5.9.1.2. Mock-ups

This is a backend development component, hence it does not require frontend interfaces.

5.9.2. Functional Specifications

The diagram in Figure 34: AD Functional Block Diagram represents the functional specifications of AD. Ambient digitalization starts by collecting data acquired at a given time frame by the AS infrastructure in the form of a list of RGBD images, one for each sensor in the AS sensors network. If AS sensors are not synchronized, the images acquired by them will not be synchronized either. In this case we proceed to synchronize them by performing timestamp alignment. Given an RGBD

image and the intrinsic parameters of the sensor that captured it, we extract a coloured 3D point cloud capturing the fragment of the working environment visible from the sensor view-point. Given the list of coloured point clouds obtained from each sensor, we perform point cloud registration to align each point cloud fragment obtaining a digital reconstruction of the working environment that incorporates information available from all the view-points. The 3D point cloud obtained this way reconstruct the working environment at a single time frame. We repeat the process described above for each time frame for which the AS sensors provide data for, until when the data streaming ends.

Figure 34: AD Functional Block Diagram

More information related to the component's functional specifications can be found in the online documentation [[LINK](#)].

5.9.3. Technical Specifications

Figure 35: AD Technical Specifications Diagram

More information related to the component's technical specifications can be found in the online documentation [[LINK](#)].

5.10. AI-PRISM CI/CD Framework (CD)

All software components use this component to support the development lifecycle. The AI-PRISM IloT Platform uses the git to manage the application repository.

5.10.1. Usage Models and Mock-ups

5.10.1.1. Usage Models

Figure 36 depicts the internal functions of the AI-PRISM CI/CD Services and the relationship to the AI-PRISM IloT Platform. Developers release new versions of software in a code repository (Git repository). This software release triggers the execution of a CI/CD pipeline in a CI/CD worker (a cloud computing resource dedicated to run the build, integration, and test scripts specified in the pipelines). If the pipeline successfully runs all the tests, a new version of the application is published in the Application repository. The cluster control function of the AI-PRISM IloT Platform fetches the versions available in the repository and notifies the administration user that there is a new version available, so that, in the end, the system administration is responsible of confirming the update process.

During the execution of the CI/CD Pipeline, the CI/CD workers use services of the AI-PRISM CI/CD to perform a software quality analysis (a static code analysis using open solutions like SonarQube¹⁶)

as well as tests in an integrated test environment (a cloud replica of a production environment) to detect possible integration issues.

Figure 36: CI/CD Use Case Diagram

5.10.1.2. Mock-ups

Mock-ups and more information related to the component's usage can be found in the online documentation [\[LINK\]](#).

5.10.2. Functional Specifications

In Figure 37: CI/CD Functional Block Diagram it can be seen the functional block diagram of the CD component.

Figure 37: CI/CD Functional Block Diagram

More information related to the component's functional specifications can be found in the online documentation [\[LINK\]](#).

5.10.3. Technical Specifications

CI/CD framework will have to guarantee building and integration of several software modules. To ensure these requirements, the framework will include the following specifications:

- **Main repository:** Gitlab repository that works on PIAP servers.
- **Integration:** It allows for cooperation with software modules created by partners
- **Build and test:** It allows you to build the software automatically and run the test
- **Validation:** Validation of a deployed solution will rely on digital twin services to perform safety risk assessments

- **Deploy:** It automatically builds binaries ready for deployment

Figure 38: CI/CD Technical Specifications Diagram

More information related to the component's technical specifications can be found in the online documentation [[LINK](#)].

5.11. AI-PRISM AI-based Perception Enhancing Modules (PE)

5.11.1. Usage Models and Mock-ups

5.11.1.1. Usage Models

PE consists of software modules that take as input the digitalized environment created by AD, and processes it to accomplish several perception-related tasks. PE modules comprehend software modules to:

- Get data from the Ambient Digitalization modules describing the current environment and actors present in it in digital form.
- Get data from database, including trained weights of the neural network models used together with prior information such as CAD models, object detections or semantic segmentation.
- Perform inference with the neural network created for the specific perception-related task at hand.
- Send PE results to the AI-PRISM modules performing task 4.3 – Agent Level Reasoning, Acting and Control, task 4.4 – Ambient Level Reasoning, Acting and Control, and task 4.5 Learning from Human Demonstration and Human-Robot Interaction.

- Store PE results in a database for later inspection and for continual learning purposes.

The main actor interacting with PE modules are the expert system administrator who develops them, and the task 4.3, 4.4, and 4.5 modules.

Figure 39: PE Use Case Diagram

More information related to the component's usage can be found in the online documentation [[LINK](#)].

5.11.1.2. Mock-ups

This is a backend development component, hence it does not require frontend interfaces.

5.11.2. Functional Specifications

The diagram in Figure 40: PE Functional Block Diagram represents the functional specifications of a perception enhancing module. A PE module takes as input the digital reconstruction of the working environment performed by AD and addresses the perception-related task at hand. At a given time

frame, input data comes as coloured point clouds representing the working scene as a collection of points with associated colour information. Each point has a six-dimensional representation containing both geometric information, in the form of its 3D coordinates (x, y, z), and photometric information, in the form of its RGB colour channels. PE modules can operate either at frame level, by producing predictions based only on static information present in the current time frame, or at video level, leveraging dynamic information accumulated across multiple time frames. To collect a video clip enabling the latter family of PE modules, a circular buffer is used to accumulate a number of consecutive time frames.

Figure 40: PE Functional Block Diagram

More information related to the component's functional specifications can be found in the online documentation [\[LINK\]](#).

5.11.3. Technical Specifications

In Figure 41: PE Technical Specifications Diagram it is shown the technical specifications of the PE component and its connection to the architecture.

Figure 41: PE Technical Specifications Diagram

More information related to the component's technical specifications can be found in the online documentation [\[LINK\]](#).

5.12. [AI-PRISM Agent Level Reasoning Enhancing Modules \(DR\)](#)

5.12.1. Usage Models and Mock-ups

5.12.1.1. Usage Models

As described in the glossary section, “agent” is a software activity that must decide about the next action that the robot should do. In that decision, it has access to the following complementary sources of knowledge/information:

- the **task(s)** that the robot is supposed to execute.
- The **environment**, or **world model**, in which the tasks are executed.
- the **perception** about the actual situation(s) that the robot is currently operating in.
- the knowledge about what actions make sense in which **situations**, to realise which tasks.
- the control **actions** that the robot can execute.

Figure 42: DR Use Case Diagram

The usage diagram in Figure 42: DR Use Case Diagram depicts DR components only at a high level and must be more concretely instantiated for each particular application context. The importance of the diagram is to make developers aware of (i) the complementary sources of information that provide the **context** of the reasoning, and (ii) the need to get properties from that context to fill in (“**configure**”) in the instances of the concrete actions that the agent reasons about.

Typically, there are three types of users that can interact with the decision making agent:

- **End user:** he can only configure a limited number of parameters of the agent, reflecting how he wants to influence the decision making/reasoning that has been programmed by the system developers, and already pre-configured by the system operators.
- **Operators:** they serve several end users, and have deeper access to the decision making; notably to the configuration of the control and perception components, and the set of tasks and world models that the reasoning agent can work with.
- **System developers:** they provide all the implementation software, and the configuration options, for both operators and end users.

5.12.1.2. *Mock-ups*

Mock-ups and more information related to the component's usage can be found in the online documentation [[LINK](#)].

5.12.2. Functional Specifications

The order in which the reasoning algorithm looks at the available information/knowledge is as follows:

- The **task** is the first piece of information to consider, because that is what the robot has to perform.
- Then, the reasoner queries the **situations** that it has knowledge about, to find one for which the right task has been defined. This is used as a candidate situation for the next step.
- The reasoner evaluates how well the selected situation fits to the available **perception** information.
- If a fit is found, it combines the information from task, situation and perception, to select the best **action** to execute, with the right configuration values for the identified context.

Figure 43: DR Functional Block Diagram

Figure 43: DR Functional Block Diagram shows the decision making (“coordination”) parts of the “reasoning”. That coordination consists of two complementary parts, more in particular, the following two coordination mechanisms work between:

1. The **coordinated** activities, namely the perception, control, task execution and world model updating activities. The “reasoning” that is required is to decide which should be the *states* of the involved activities (perception, control, world model updating and task execution) that should be activated at every particular moment in time. A *state* is one of the possible behaviours of that activity, and the possible choices, and transitions between these choices, is represented/implemented as a **Finite State Machine** in the coordinated *activity*.
2. The **Petri Net** in the “reasoning” activity: Petri Nets are complementary to Finite State Machines, because they “mediate” the events that are sent to, and received from, a set of coordinated activities. That mediation is based on the knowledge about what activity states and configurations are allowed and “best”, for the agent as a whole.

More information related to the component's functional specifications can be found in the online documentation [[LINK](#)]. Each application comes with its own variety of agent behaviours, and hence of inter-activity coordination and configuration.

5.12.3. Technical Specifications

Because of the just-mentioned large variety of activity and agent behaviours, we can give no concrete technical specifications in this overview document. Except for these generic software design insights:

- **Events:** They are generated inside activities, and “broadcasted” to other activities, that can react to them.
- **Event processing:** The “mediator”/“reasoner” is the only activity that has the knowledge about which coordinated activities *must* react to which events. Hence, it “listens” to all events of all the activities it coordinates, and filters only the relevant ones. The selected events are fed to its internal Petri Net, which will “fire” from time to time, generating new events that must be given back to (a selection of) the coordinated activities.
- **Event communication:** The above-mentioned “filtering” typically also involves the *translation* of the event names from the activity-specific versions to the agent-specific meanings. As well as the choice of the appropriate communication channels between activities; these can indeed be deployed inside the shared memory space of one single process; or in different processes on the same computer; or on different computers connected by wired or wireless message transport channels.

More information related to the component's technical specifications can be found in the online documentation [[LINK](#)].

5.13. [AI-PRISM AI-based Ambient Level Reasoning Modules \(CR\)](#)

5.13.1. Usage Models and Mock-ups

5.13.1.1. *Usage Models*

The main objective of the AI-based ambient level reasoning modules is to coordinate all agents within a dynamic collaborative ambient. To do so, three agents related to the management and administration of these ambient-level reasoning modules have been identified for this usage model. These agents interact with different tools or interfaces that would allow the proper interaction with the system. They are grouped separately according to the action purpose, which is explained below:

Figure 44: AI-PRISM AI-based Ambient Level Reasoning Module Use Case Diagram

- Browse and Select:** It involves browsing the catalog of available reasoning modules and all actions related to the navigation through the different modules for ambient level reasoning that are available for deployment and use. Two actors should access the “Browse and Select” interface: the production manager, who knows which applications are needed and requests them to be installed, and the system administrator (Sys. admin), who manages and deploys those modules within the system.
- Configure.** Once a tool is installed, some configuration is needed to fit the environment where it is deployed, including the Industrial Process Definition. It can be separated into two levels:
 - Configure System Connections:** Sys. admin makes sure the configuration of the system is correct, that it is correctly connected to the rest of the system and other modules if necessary (Configure System connections). For instance, this activity involves configuring the connections to other corporative software, like the Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP).
 - Configure Reasoning:** In contrast, the Production Manager ensures that all the inputs required by the reasoning modules are correct. This implies verifying if the industrial processes are correctly defined. For instance, is the information regarding production

orders, Bills of Materials (BoMs), resources, worker shifts, etc. correct? It also implies configuring or validating if the configuration of the triggering events that will guide the execution of the reasoning modules is correct.

- **Validate Reasoning.** Production Managers can also request the execution of a reasoning module for a given input or set of inputs, so that the reasoning module takes the configured input data and returns as an output the reasoning result (e.g. an action to take). The production manager can then check the reasoning results and, if these results are in agreement with the given goal to achieve, validate the reasoning. For instance, the production manager can get the result of a planning or scheduling module for a specific set of production orders to validate the results.
- **Monitor Process Execution Performance:** Operators and Production Managers can monitor the execution of the industrial production process in the collaboration ambient, to monitor the performance of the process and to assess if it is aligned with the targeted goals. The reasoning modules will take actions automatically to ensure these goals (based on the provided configurations) and will also recommend or suggest actions to the persons involved in the process to facilitate an adequate response to unexpected events. Operators and Production Managers can also visualize the performance of previous (historic) production process executions.
- **Explain reasoning:** In some cases, the actions made by the program, or the applied changes require some extra explanation for the Production Manager or the Operator to fully understand it, or to provide more data that might help make decisions. These interfaces should provide them with it when necessary.

5.13.1.2. *Mock-ups*

Mock-ups and more information related to the component's usage can be found in the online documentation [[LINK](#)].

5.13.2. Functional Specifications

The functional specifications detailed in the diagram start with the modelling and definition of the industrial processes the reasoning modules will act upon. This implies that the inputs coming either from the users (e.g. through a configuration interface as mentioned in the previous section) or external systems (normally the ERP) will be transformed into a model of the industrial process that the reasoning modules can understand and reason with. These models will also define the tasks (or operations, or units of work) that will be executed by the agents (robots or humans) in the collaboration agent. These definitions of the operations do not necessarily need to include low level

descriptions of the robot programming (for instance, path trajectories), but rather, higher-level definitions relevant for operations management. An example of a task can be 'paint piece with code 09890'. These high-level models will be linked to other lower-level models used for programming or reasoning at the agent level, and will include models of the (time) performance of the execution of the task, which can be used for operations management at the ambient level (e.g. planning, scheduling, operations control). Again, this might imply transforming or processing low-level models to extract the information that is relevant for operations management. The tasks defined should also be approved by production managers, so that they explicitly agree that the performance of the individual task is in agreement with the objectives of the company. Based on these definitions, each reasoning module will implement functions to request a reasoning result (for instance to create a task scheduling or assign tasks to robots in the ambient) that will be triggered by the user or an external system through an input, and will generate a reasoning result conveying a set of coordination actions in the collaboration ambient. For instance, the result of a task scheduling module will be a detailed schedule of the execution of tasks coordinating different agents in the ambient. The user may approve the resulting decisions or actions, or request a different result, so as to establish a target overall process performance. For instance, the production manager can request a production scheduling or an assignment of tasks to agents, and approve these results if they provide an acceptable performance according to different criteria, so that they can be used in production. These actions will be also expressed using the industrial process model definitions.

During the industrial process, control operations will utilise information about the collaborative environment as input. Using this input, they will evaluate the current process performance and take

corrective actions when necessary, such as rescheduling or reassigning tasks to agents if the performance falls short of the target.

Figure 45: AI-PRISM AI-based Ambient Level Reasoning Module Functional Block Diagram

This reasoning module can be applied in different ways depending on the use case and its specifications, providing a new schedule or planification according on the configuration and the input data. The diagram below shows an example of how this module works for the Andrew World use case, providing the production schedule and adapting it to the availability of resources for the daily production if necessary.

As it can be seen in this functional diagram, in the AW use case the Ambient level reasoning module provides a new weekly schedule by the end of every week (each Friday) based on the pending work orders, materials and production capacity of the factory, providing a daily production plan is based on it. This daily schedule can be modified if necessary. Once the plan is accepted, it can be sent to production and start the process. Through the process, the ambient status input and other sensor input parameters are monitored and, if they are not within acceptable parameters, a corrective action is applied to the rest of the daily plan if necessary.

Figure 46: AI-PRISM AI-based Ambient Level Reasoning Module Functional Block Diagram applied to AW use case

More information related to the component's functional specifications can be found in the online documentation [[LINK](#)].

5.13.3. Technical Specifications

The technical specification diagram in Figure 47: AI-PRISM AI-based Ambient Level Reasoning Module Technical Specifications Diagram represents the inner architecture of an ambient reasoning module (a task scheduler) and its main technical components. Each module will implement an end application microservice which will provide all the user interfaces described in previous sections. A modelling backend service will be used to connect internal components to the industrial process databases that will be deployed in the AI-PRISM Data Platform Services. A northbound communication module will be used to connect to other enterprise systems like the ERP. The frontend application will be connected to the task scheduler, which is the technical component that encapsulates the reasoning logic. During the execution of the production process, the operations control component will be connected to the message broker of the AI-PRISM Data Platform Service to receive information updating the actual status of the collaboration ambient and, based on this information, connect to the task scheduler service if rescheduling is required to ensure the target performance.

Figure 47: AI-PRISM AI-based Ambient Level Reasoning Module Technical Specifications Diagram

More information related to the component's technical specifications can be found in the online documentation [\[LINK\]](#).

5.14. AI-PRISM Human – Machine Interaction Modules (HI)

5.14.1. Usage Models and Mock-ups

5.14.1.1. Usage Models

The main objective of the HMI module is to provide the necessary interfaces between the human workers and the robotic agents during two important phases of human-robot collaborative tasks.

The first phase, referred to as the **demonstration phase**, consists of allowing the human to teach through demonstration the task (or part of the task) that is desired to be executed by the robot. If only motion is important to specify the task, the demonstrator can opt for teaching using kinaesthetic

teaching (hand-guiding the robot while performing the task) or via passive observation. The latter refers to the robotic system “observing” what the human does to perform the task while remaining still. This can be done by designing specific tools that facilitate the demonstration while tracking the motion (i.e., position and orientation). On the other hand, if not only motion but also interaction forces and moments are important (e.g., in assembly operations or other operations that require contact), then forces and moments are also recorded and later on provided to the learning model. More details on the programming by demonstrations are given in section 5.15.

The second phase, the **execution phase**, executes a skill that allows human-robot interaction. HMIs must, therefore, allow this interaction by communicating information from the human to the robot. For example, if the human wants to disturb the trajectory of the robot (e.g., to hold a tool or to stop a robotic arm), this can be done via force interaction (by measuring end effector forces/moments or joint torques). This HMI/sensor information would be mapped accordingly and interpreted at setpoints that are sent to a continuous motion controller. These setpoints can be desired force, torque, velocity, or rotational velocity that are sent to the controller. The exact interpretation in terms of behaviour is specified in the constraint-based specification language of the robot controller (see section 5.15). The HMI/sensor information can also be mapped at the discrete level, for example, by pressing a button to indicate the pause, and this would be sent instead to a state coordinator (e.g., finite state machine).

The transfer of information is not only from human to machine, but also from machine to human. HMIs inform the operator about the states of the robot to improve situation awareness and avoid mode confusion. Different modalities exist and can be used depending on the application and the context. For example, LED red lights can be used to indicate problems with the task execution or the machine. Or, during demonstration when there is physical interaction between human and robot force interaction can be used to implicitly communicate to the operator. Graphical user interfaces to also belong to this category.

Section 5.15 (programming by demonstration) uses the HMI to interact with the operator during both the demonstration phase and the execution phase. Compared to the use case diagram in section 5.15, this diagram offers more detail on the demonstration phase and execution phase.

During demonstration the **demonstrator** interacts with the HMI in order to demonstrate the subtask at hand (right side of the use case diagram). Two approaches are envisioned to demonstrate:

- Kinaesthetic teaching, i.e., the demonstrator takes the robot in hand, while the robot is following the demonstrator using a force/torque sensor and a force-controlled behaviour.
- Passive observation, i.e., a tracking device is handled by the demonstrator and is tracked by the system (e.g., an HTC-Vive hand tracker, or an Opti-track marker-based system)

When also interaction forces are of importance to the application, passive observation system is preferred because such a system introduces less force disturbances to the demonstration. In these cases, the tracking device is extended with a force torque sensor.

Additionally, the demonstrations also include data segmentation and interaction with the learning algorithm, this is handled by a discrete-event HMI. This discrete-event type of HMI can be a button/light system or a graphical user interface.

During execution of the nominal application (left side of the use case diagram), it is the **operator** that still can interact with the system. An example of such an interaction is indicating to the robot system that the operator is back and wants to take over the task at hand.

Figure 48: HI Use Case Diagram

5.14.1.2. Mock-ups

More information related to the component's usage can be found in the online documentation [[LINK](#)].

This is a backend/hardware development component; hence it does not require frontend interfaces. Therefore, no mock-up is provided. A mock-up *scenario* is explained in section 5.15 (programming by demonstration).

5.14.2. Functional Specifications

The functional block diagram in Figure 49: HI Functional block diagram explains a typical flow chart for the demonstration phase and the execution phase.

In the demonstration phase, nominal parts of the application are running until a subtask is reached where the force/motion interaction needs to be adapted to the site/location/task at hand. The robot application pauses until the demonstrator signals a start, for example by pressing a button, and the force/motion interaction is recorded. This continues until a set of demonstrations of sufficient quality is obtained.

During the execution phase, the demonstrations and the extracted model of the force/motion interaction is combined with the constraint-based specification that the application developer has made. This allows the system to execute the task at hand. During execution there still can be interactions with the operator. The appropriate reaction to disturbances or input of the operator is described using the constraint-based task specification language explained in section 5.15. This is combined with discrete-event coordination to handle starting/stopping/resuming/recovering. The flow chart on the right gives a simple example of such a coordination.

The diagrams illustrate the functional specification of the AI-PRISM HMI modules during the demonstration and execution phases.

Figure 49: HI Functional block diagram

More information related to the component's functional specifications can be found in the online documentation [\[LINK\]](#).

5.14.3. Technical Specifications

An HMI module is part of the eTaSL controller explained in section 5.15. It consists basically of two parts:

- Hardware abstraction Orocos components (*HMI Modules*) that know how to communicate with the hardware at hand (e.g., an HTC-Vive system or a force sensor)
- A constraint-based description of how these signals relate to the task at hand (described in the eTaSL specification language). These will be added to the rest of the constraint-based description and executed by the *eTaSL constraint-based controller*

Figure 50: Architectural diagram situating the HMI modules depicts how these parts interact.

Figure 50: Architectural diagram situating the HMI modules

As described in [12], the robot behaviour can be constructed from a number of building blocks (i.e. groups of constraints), of which there are basically two types:

- **RAM** (reactive action model) that describes nominal behaviour and how to deviate from this nominal behaviour in case of disturbances
- **SIM** (sensor interaction model) that describes a set of constraints that define the interaction with sensor information. HMI-related constraints are of this type.

In other words, the constraint-based approach allows us to decouple the specification of what to do with the HMI from the other constraints of the robot system. For a particular execution of the robot application or demonstration, these building blocks are assembled into one eTaSL specification.

Within AI-Prism, we can distinguish between the following types of constraints (building blocks):

- Robot-related constraints (typically from URDF)
- Environment-related constraints (typically modelled by the application developer, can involve additional sensors)
- Task-related constraints
- HMI-related constraints.

More information related to the component's technical specifications can be found in the online documentation [[LINK](#)].

5.15. AI-PRISM Programming by Demonstration (PD) Environment

5.15.1. Usage Models and Mock-ups

5.15.1.1. *Usage Models*

The main objective of the AI-Prism programming by demonstration environment is to quickly deploy robot applications. To do so, generic applications are assembled and configured from a library of skills. These generic applications, also called "robot apps". These generic applications are then further specialized for a specific factory site using programming by demonstration. Different actors are involved in the process of deploying a new application. The proposed approach supports each of these actors in a different way. In some cases, the different actors are roles that can be fulfilled by the same person:

The **system developer** is a robotics and control expert that develops a set of skills that define how the robot behaves and reacts to inputs. A few examples of skills are given in the mockup example below. The formulation of these skills is aided by using a constraint-based task specification language and corresponding controller¹² and rFSM state machines¹³ ()

The **application developer** assembles, configures and coordinates the above skills into an application. He is an expert in the application domain and is capable of developing configuration scripts. He decides on what skills will be used and what parts of the application will be obtained using programming-by-demonstration. His objective is to combine model-based programming and

¹² <https://etasl.pages.gitlab.kuleuven.be/>

¹³ <https://github.com/kmarkus/rFSM>

programming-by-demonstration such that the application can be deployed with only a minimal number of demonstrations. His work is facilitated by an appropriate set of skills developed by the system developer.

The **demonstrator** is a human worker that is allowed to perform minor configurations on the robot system and will be trained in how to perform the demonstrations. His work is facilitated by an appropriately defined generic application.

The **operator** is the day-to-day human worker that performs tasks in cooperation with the robot system. The system not only has to react to disturbances or actions of the operator, also environmental or work piece related disturbances can influence the execution. They are indicated by the **environmental disturbances** actor.

Figure 51: PD Use Case Diagram

5.15.1.2. *Mock-ups*

This is a backend/hardware development component, hence it does not require frontend interfaces. Instead a mockup-scenario inspired on the KEBA pilot is explained below. Many of the details of this specific example are subject to change:

- There is a library with a set of skills such as a skill to avoid humans in the environment for a force-controlled insertion or a skill to use vision to grasp a printed circuit board (PCB).
- The generic application could be placing a PCB in a holder, where the PCB is located using vision, and where the fitting with narrow tolerances of the PCB is aided using force control, and the human worker in the environment is avoided.
- The demonstrator deploys the application to a specific factory site for a specific holder and PCB-type by using programming by demonstration (PbD) to demonstrate a number of position/force trajectories using one of the HMI modalities. These are then used to learn a statistical distribution of allowable trajectories used for execution.
- The generic application and the models and parameters learned from demonstration are then used during execution.
- During execution the operator works in the environment of the robot. Additional constraints on the allowable trajectories are added to avoid the operator and to impose the location determined by vision. These additional constraints are continuously updated to deal with (observed) disturbances.

In the above example, there could be many deployed applications, corresponding to different combinations of PCB's, holders and robot-cells.

More information related to the component's usage can be found in the online documentation [\[LINK\]](#).

5.15.2. Functional Specifications

The diagram in Figure 52 represents the functional specification of the AI-Prism PbD environment. Considering a library of skills, the application developer makes an analysis of the definition of the application to determine whether any new skills are required to be added to the library. The system developer develops new skills. Such a new skill consists of constraint-based task specifications in the eTaSL language and of finite state machines described in rFSM. The eTaSL controller can interpret these specifications and execute a robot controller with the defined behaviour. These skills describe how the robot should behave and how it should react to disturbances. It can not only contain aspects of reactive control such as force-control or visual servoing, but also basic motion planning. After a validation cycle, newly defined skills are added to the library and used to configure and assemble skills into a "generic" application.

In these application specifications, aspects of some tasks are left open and are handled by a programming-by-demonstration model. These demonstrations do more than just a teach-in of a trajectory, they specify the nominal value and the allowable variations of some degrees of freedom in the application. These can be trajectories, forces or other aspects of the task. At execution this demonstration model will be combined with the previously mentioned constraints in order to determine the concrete motion.

Often, the same generic application, will be used multiple times in different contexts: e.g., another factory site, with different work pieces or in a different work cell. Demonstrations will be performed in order to deploy the generic application to these specific contexts.

Figure 52 : PD functional block diagram

More information related to the component's functional specifications can be found in the online documentation [\[LINK\]](#).

5.15.3. Technical Specifications

The technical specification diagram in Figure 53 represents the overall architecture of the robot controller. The constraint-based robot controller is a reactive controller that needs to run at a higher sample frequency (order of magnitude 100Hz). The Orocos real-time component system RTT¹⁴ is used to write real-time components. Orocos offers lock-free, thread-safe inter-component communication in a single process. The 5C's¹⁵ (computation, communication, coordination, composition and configuration) can be configured from the outside of the components, resulting in a flexible framework for real-time components in robotics.

Hardware (robots, sensors, ...) and other external inputs and outputs are handled using hardware abstraction components such as robot drivers and sensor drivers. There is an Orocos-ROS and Orocos-ROS2 bridge to facilitate communication in a ROS environment.

GUI and visualization (if needed) is done as a node in the ROS environment.

The eTaSL constraint-based controller component can flexibly connect to Orocos communication ports and expose this in the constraint-based task specification language. This allows to write a constraint-based task specification in two mostly independent parts: a part describing the properties and constraints related to the robot system, and a part describing the skill or application.

When used with programming-by-demonstration, the constraint-based robot task specification consists of two parts:

- a probabilistic description of the demonstrated force/motion interactions describing nominal force/motion and the allowable variations on this nominal force/motion.
- a model-based task constraint-based task description describing the parts of the task that is known before-hand. The constraints are described in a LUA-based language called eTaSL¹⁶.

The robot controller computes robot motions that satisfy optimally these two parts of the task specification.

Low-level coordination of control-subtasks is done using a lightweight state-chart implementation rFSM¹⁷. The HMI module is further detailed in section 5.14.

¹⁴ <https://docs.orocos.org/>

¹⁵ <https://robmosys.pages.gitlab.kuleuven.be/composable-and-explainable-systems-of-systems.pdf#sec%3Apattern-systems-5Cs-architecture>

¹⁶ <https://etasl.pages.gitlab.kuleuven.be/>

¹⁷ <https://github.com/kmarkus/rFSM>

Figure 53: Architectural diagram for programming-by-demonstration

More information related to the component's technical specifications can be found in the online documentation [\[LINK\]](#).

5.16. AI-PRISM Human Safety Management Procedures (SP)

5.16.1. Usage Models and Mock-ups

The system permits to solve most problems related to the positioning and motion of machines, robots and human workers in factories, with different sizes, needs, and hazard levels. These Use Cases are:

- Localization
- Collision Prevention
- Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) Control
- Hazardous Zone Fencing

The system is designed to manage hazards, increase workers safety or protect workers, complying with the GDPR legislation, and to allow robotic agents, human workers and vehicles monitoring in different context thanks to its high modularity and scalability. Following are listed all the use cases with a detailed description for the significant use cases identified as objective of the implementation, and with a more generic description for the other ones.

Furniture: collaborative robots in painting process

In this use case a cobot system should be able to recognize objects, such as furniture pieces in the environment, perform painting and sanding processes under the supervision of a human operator. During these operations the cobot rotates the furniture in the three positions of the frame. To ensure that the operator works in a safe environment, the system allows the administrator to set safety thresholds that represent the distance between the human and robot, monitors the environment, sends a warning notification to the operator in case these thresholds are exceeded, and registers it on the platform.

Electronics: reduction of environmental pollution with waste from production of semiconductors

In this use case an operator put glue on the top of a stick, a cobot takes the stick from the operator hand and transfer a chip to the positioning table. During this process the cobot and the human work in the same space, increasing collision probability. To ensure safety between human worker and cobot, the system follows the same steps described before in the furniture use case.

Foods & Beverage: brewery/food industry transformation towards Industry

This use case has two macro-cases. The first one involves the usage of a cobot to lift sacks of filtration powder from a stack to a conveyor. Once the stack is empty a forklift refill it. An operator supervises all the operations. The environment of this first case is particularly dangerous both for the proximity of the robot and the forklift to the operator. The human-safety solution is an active assistance system which monitors the environment, stop the robots and vehicles that could generate potential hazards. This solution involves the use of two types of cameras, to enable computer vision methods. The second macro-case is the packaging and palletizing of a customer order. In this context a cobot supports the operator, transporting the crates from the worker station to the shipping area, and following the operator. The security platform can identify bottles outside the crates in specific area in which they should not be present. A suitable number of CCTV cameras are installed in the working area, linked to an on-edge computing unit. Bespoken computer vision algorithms allow the detection of hazardous events through the recognition of dangerous object or collisions. When the hazard is detected, the on-edge unit sends a message to the platform which registers the event and notifies the operators through visual and audio stimuli.

Home Appliances: Adaptable & Collaborative Workstation for Packaging & Quality Control of Hoods Human & Cobots

In this use case are considered 3 types of scenarios involving different numbers of human workers and robotic agents. In all the scenarios the cobots and the humans perform actions in sequence. Cobots perform tasks such as: grounding test, functioning test, sticking metal label, barcode labeling. Operators perform tasks

such as: cable packing, sticking of cable, filter assembling, bagging the product. As operators and cobots work in the same space it can be adopted the same solution proposed in the electronics use case.

Discrete Manufacturing: AI-Control for Natural, Multi-modal Collaboration

This use case involves several operations for PCB testing: recognition, grasping, manipulation, positioning. Each one is performed by an operator and can be supported by a cobot. Operator and cobots works in the same space, thus it can be adopted the same solution proposed in the electronics use case.

5.16.1.1.Usage Models

The System Developer has the task of identifying critical issues in the plants together with the HSE Manager and defining the use cases to be implemented to improve safety. Once the use cases have been defined, the necessary information is collected in the plant to apply the use cases, if the information is not present, the installation of dedicated HW is required (cameras, stereoscopies cameras, beacons, other sensors). All information must be submitted to the Safety Management Platform. The application developer has the task of configuring the rules to be applied based on the information received. The HSE Manager will have to identify the corrective procedure that the workers will have to implement for each safety violation detected. Human workers must apply the procedures defined by the HSE in terms of Safety, in case of violations detected by the system they must apply corrective actions.

Figure 54: Use Case Diagram Human Safety Management Procedure

Figure 55 shows the use case diagram for the Foods & Beverage use case, particularly the macro-case of the filtration powder, that is the one on which the human-safety system is implemented. In this case the computation unit is wired with the on-field cameras, stereo-cameras for the forklift and on-edge cameras for the cobot. The Computational Unit verifies that the position of the operator is in the safety area. When a human worker becomes an obstacle, entering in the working space of the cobot or the forklift, the computational unit sends a stop signal to both the cobot and the forklift. Also, it sends an alarm to the system so that it can store the hazard event. The forklift and the cobot immediately stop working when they receive the stop signal. The user is alerted from the alarm device present on field and can start to adopt the HSE procedure. After the hazard events are stored on the system the HSE manager can visualize the actual event and all the history on the platform.

Figure 55: Use Case Diagram for the Foods & Beverage - filtration powder use case

Also, in this use case diagram is possible to see the different actions that a HSE Manager can perform on the platform: manage users, workers, groups, and view hazard KPIs.

5.16.1.2. *Mock-ups*

Mock-ups and more information related to the component's usage can be found in the online documentation [[LINK](#)].

5.16.2. Functional Specifications

The diagram below represents an example of implementation for access control to an area in which a robot operates.

Figure 56: General Functional Diagram

Following are described function diagrams related to Foods & Beverage use case.

Foods & Beverage: brewery/food industry transformation towards Industry – filtration powder preparation

For this use case the functional diagram of the safety platform, Figure 57, shows that the platform needs to be feed with some information. First is working area parameters, which define the monitored

areas. Second one is the collision threshold, that is the minimum distance between two entities, like forklift-operator or cobot-operator. When these parameters are configured the system is listening for hazard events. If an alarm is sent from the field the platform registers, shows the event and update the events history.

Figure 57: Athenian Brewery Safety Platform Functional Diagram

Figure 58: Athenian Brewery Safety Platform Functional Diagram – other functionalities

In Figure 58 are shown the following Safety Platform functionalities: add/delete users, workers, groups, assign roles, show actual events, events history and hazard KPIs. All these functionalities are generic and valid for all the use cases of the project.

From the field side, Figure 59, some ambient data are collected from cameras and sensors. Through entity recognition modules and location computation is possible to determine if some human workers are present in the working area. In this case the position of the operators is compared with the one of the cobot and/or the forklift. If the distance between them is less than the collision threshold configured on the platform by the HSE administrator, then, simultaneously, a stop command is sent to the cobot/forklift, an alarm is sent to the operator device to inform him about the danger and the event info are sent to the platform to store data.

Figure 59: Athenian Brewery field Functional Diagram

More information related to the component's functional specifications can be found in the online documentation [\[LINK\]](#).

5.16.3. Technical Specifications

The safety management solution will be a three-level platform. The first level is an AI edge computer layer for local sensor information processing, the second level is a FOG computer layer that has the task of applying the rules required by the use cases (the FOG computing layer may not always be necessary). The last level is a cloud platform layer which has the task of displaying and logging all the alarms and configuring the FOG and edge levels.

Figure 60: High-Level Technical Architecture

Following is described the high-level technical architecture related to Foods & Beverage use case.

Foods & Beverage: brewery/food industry transformation towards Industry – filtration powder preparation

The architecture is composed by 3 main layers. A Field Layer that contains sensors, cameras and alarm device to inform the operator of a hazard. From this level video flows and sensors data are sent to the On-Edge Layer. In this level a computer vision module implements Machine Learning models running on-board on computational units to search for entities, like human workers, in the working space. A Hazard Orchestrator evaluates if a hazard event, like a collision, is possible. If the event is happening the Orchestrator sends an alarm to the operator and stop command to the involved machines (cobots or forklift). Simultaneously it sends events data to the upper layer, through a set of Rest API. In the Cloud Layer the backend module stores the event and update the KPIs. Also, it instantly shows the event on the map of the monitored area.

Figure 61: Athenian Brewery - filtration powder use case High Level Technical Architecture

More information related to the component's technical specifications can be found in the online documentation [\[LINK\]](#).

5.17. AI-PRISM Open Access Network Portal

5.17.1. Usage Models and Mock-ups

5.17.1.1. Usage Models

The AI-PRISM Open Access Network Portal (AI-PRISM-NetPort) contains four engines as presented in Figure 62. AI-PRISM-NetPort Use Case Diagram. These engines will provide the following functionalities as follows:

- The **Training and Certification Engine (NetPort-TEC)** will provide the services to the end users regarding the training, examination and certifications to access the pilots.

- The **Contracts and the Finance Engine (NetPort-CFE)** will provide the service to manage and handle the negotiations, agreement, contracts and the payments between the end users.
- The **Virtual Pilots Engine (NetPort-VPE)** will allow the end users to create, deploy and provide the services of the virtual pilot.
- The **Planning and Scheduling Engine (NetPort-PSE)** will allow the end users to schedule the access to the pilots. This scheduling will be optimized targeting different objectives based on the end user’s preference.

Figure 62. AI-PRISM-NetPort Use Case Diagram

5.17.1.2. Mock-ups

Mock-ups and more information related to the component's usage can be found in the online documentation [\[LINK\]](#).

5.17.2. Functional Specifications

The following are 8 UML activity diagrams that describes the main activities in the Open Access Pilots Portal.

Figure 63. Virtual Pilot Engine Functional Specifications; on the left the activity diagram for creating the virtual pilot, on the right the activity diagram for using the virtual pilot by the end user

Figure 64. Training and Certification Engine Functional Specifications; on the left Activity diagram for creating the training materials in the virtual pilot, on the right the activity diagram for completing the pilot access criteria

Figure 65. Contracts and Finance Engine Functional Specifications; on the left the activity for adding terms to the pilots, on the right the activity for negotiating and agreeing on the usage and financial terms

Figure 66. Planning and Scheduling Engine Functional Specifications; on the left the activity for adding the pilot to the scheduling engine, on the right the activity for scheduling the pilot physical access

More information related to the component's functional specifications can be found in the online documentation [\[LINK\]](#).

5.17.3. Technical Specification

The AI-PRISM-NetPort will include the following components:

1. User access control and security
 - a. User and companies' information manager: this component will manage and handle the information of the pilots and users
 - b. User access manager: this component will manage the access levels of the users with the different pilots and related information.
2. Web interface: this component will allow the user to interact with the portal. The aim to provide all functionalities via web base interface.
3. Contract and Finance Engine
 - a. Negotiation and Contracts Manager: handles the negotiations in the portal.
 - b. Payment Manger: handles the payment in the portal.
4. Planning and Scheduling Engine
 - a. Needs and Services Matching Manager: provide the match-making feature once the user search for an open access pilot with certain features.
 - b. Scheduling optimizer: optimizes the schedules of the pilot access for both the pilot side and the end user side.
5. Virtual Pilots Engine
 - a. Virtual Pilot Space Manger: provide the virtual space which will allow the pilot owners to share and deploy the virtual pilot with possible beneficiary end users.
6. Training and Certification Engine
 - a. Training and teaching manger: provides the teaching and training services to the end users.
 - b. Examination and evaluation manger: examines and certifies the access to the pilots.

Figure 67: NS Technical Specifications Diagram

More information related to the component's technical specifications can be found in the online documentation [[LINK](#)]. In addition, the figure above will be continuously updated as the development work progresses. The diagram in Figure 67: NS Technical Specifications Diagram does not show the data flow yet as the architecture is under development at the time of submitting this deliverable.

6. Implementation Guidelines

6.1. [Implementation Calendar](#)

The DOA provides a description of the planning of design (WP2), implementation (WP3-WP5), and demonstration and validation activities in AI-PRISM. As stated in the DOA, the project will follow a hybrid agile-waterfall approach for software development. A complete release of the Reference Framework and Specification will be released in M6 to kick-off development activities, which start in M7 and are organized in periodic releases or sprints. The design of the Reference Architecture is not finalized until M12. This overlap between the architecture design exercise and the development activities allows to feed back to the reference architecture the results and the knowledge gained from actual development, aligned with the agile principle of delivering early and continuously.

The demonstration and validation activities are also executed in parallel. Linked to the industrial scenarios and requirements analysis (WP1), the process starts with the collection of requirements in pilot use cases, which runs in parallel and feeds to the Reference Architecture and the definition of functional and technical specifications. Furthermore, AI-PRISM solutions are human-centric thanks to the integration of Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) from the identification of requirements for the design of new systems to the final stage of evaluation and validation. The project benefits from human analysis techniques that capture both quantitative measures as well as qualitative rich data across the different demonstrators (WP5), delivering an initial report (First Task Analysis for benchmarking and design requirements) in M6. Besides this, the integration of solutions in industrial environments (WP5) starts as early as in M12, so that training data can be collected on-site, and solutions can further evolve based on user feedback in pilot scenarios. This planning is as mentioned reflected in the description of the action and summarized in the Gantt chart of the DOA included in Figure .

Figure 68 AI-PRISM Gantt chart (source DOA)

The objective of this section is to provide a general planning of activities to effectively implement the methodology envisioned in the DOA, organizing development activities into a calendar that is consistent with the overall project plan and methodologies. In particular, the development of AI-enhancing tools and the generation of realistic simulation environments requires the collection of

large amounts of training data, and this needs to be considered in the planning, and well aligned with the activities needed to commission the hardware to realise the pilot demonstrators.

The approach is to consider the following calendar phases for all activities:

1. **Initial definition phase (M1-M6):** This phase focuses on producing an initial set of requirements, specifications, and reference architecture design so that development activities can start as soon as possible. It frames the human analysis activities conducted in WP5 collecting data in situ on pilots to ensure human centred design.
2. **Early prototyping phase (M7-M12):** This phase conveys the first months of the development activities. The requirements and specifications are reviewed iteratively together with the end users, and mockups, early prototypes and proof of concepts are used to validate alternative design proposals. The solutions are not integrated in the industrial environments of the pilots, so it is not possible to collect training data on-site, or at least, it is not possible to collect training data using sensors or data infrastructure that are not already available in the industrial scenarios. In this phase, the focus is on co-design and validation with industrial owners, and on integrating the different AI-PRISM components together. Training data is collected in laboratory conditions.
3. **Integration phase (M13-M18):** This phase starts with the release of the first version of the AI-PRISM components that implements the interfaces defined in the reference architecture (Milestone 5) in M12. The focus is to integrate the components in the industrial pilots, and start the procurement and engineering of the hardware components, which for robotic components such as robotic arms or Autonomous Mobile Robots (AMRs) can span for several months. The procurement and integration of the sensors and edge and fog equipment required to build training data sets so that data can be collected in the industrial scenarios as early as possible.
4. **Commissioning phase (M19-M24):** In this phase, the commissioning of all the required equipment is completed. The end of this phase corresponds to Milestone 6. All the hardware is installed in the demonstration scenarios, and all the solutions are ready to be tested on-site, including the AI-PRISM Open Access Pilot.
5. **Improvement phase (M25-M36):** From M25 and until the end of the project, the improvement phase comprises the collection and preparation of data collected on-site to re-train the models, and the improvement of all solutions through experiments with end users at the pilot sites. It includes the major third release of all solutions (Milestone 7, M30), the final validation and demonstration, and the final release of the software (Milestone 8, M36)

Figure represents this overall planning of activities.

Figure 69 Overall planning of activities

ANNEX A: References

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